

3SIM: Blockchain Simulator for Investigating the Blockchain Trilemma

Bachelor's Thesis of

Davis Riedel

At the KIT Department of Informatics
Institute for Software Design and Quality (SDQ)
Institute of Applied Informatics and Formal Description Methods (AIFB)

First examiner: Prof. Dr. Ralf Reussner (SDQ)
Second examiner: Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Robert Heinrich (SDQ)
First advisor: Dr.-Ing. Niclas Kannengießer (AIFB)

26. May 2025 – 26. September 2025

Abstract

Blockchain systems serve diverse use-cases, whereas each use-case imposes distinct non-functional requirements [1; 2; 3; 4]. The *blockchain trilemma* states that it is impossible to simultaneously maximize the *degree of decentralization* (DoD), scalability and security of a blockchain system [5; 6; 7]. Software architects must balance the trade-offs between DoD, scalability and security, to meet the non-functional requirements for their use-case [5]. It is difficult to estimate how the blockchain trilemma manifests in a concrete blockchain system, before deploying it. It is costly and tedious to deploy a real-world blockchain system for each iteration [8]. Therefore, a tool is needed that helps software architects to better understand how blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. Simulations offer a resource-efficient approach to investigate large-scale blockchain systems [3; 8]. *This thesis presents 3SIM, a flexible software-architecture-focused blockchain simulator for investigating the blockchain trilemma.*

3SIM is a *discrete-event simulator* that includes a metamodel and a stochastic simulation model. The metamodel of 3SIM enables software-architecture-focused modelling of blockchain system configurations. 3SIM can be run as an Eclipse plugin. 3SIM builds upon SM-SIM, a blockchain simulator for simulating selfish-mining attacks [8]. 3SIM computes multiple output metrics that are suitable to assess the DoD, scalability and security of the simulated blockchain system [5].

Experiments are conducted to demonstrate the plausibility and utility of results produced by 3SIM. In each experiment, an input parameter was varied while the other input parameters remained as in a common base configuration, in order to assess the influence of the varied parameter on the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. The varied parameters are *mean block creation interval*, *maximum block size*, *throughput and latency* of links between validating nodes, *number of required security confirmations*, and *hashing power distribution* among validating nodes.

The conducted experiments show, that scalability of a blockchain system improves with longer *mean block creation interval* ($\overline{I_B}$) and less *number of required security confirmations* ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$). Very short and very large $\overline{I_B}$ negatively impact scalability. A longer $\overline{I_B}$ improves the security of a blockchain system in terms of availability, but at the cost of consistency, which is an inherent trade-off [5]. A faster P2P network facilitates better scalability and security. DoD improves if validating nodes have an equal distribution of hashing power and are equally distributed across geographical regions.

3SIM helps software architects to gain a better understanding of how blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma, and helps them

to quickly and iteratively assess how the blockchain trilemma manifests in a concrete blockchain system, before deploying it.

Zusammenfassung

Blockchain Systeme werden in zahlreichen Bereichen angewandt, wobei jeder Anwendungsbereich eigene nicht-funktionale Anforderungen stellt [1; 2; 3; 4]. Das *Blockchain Trilemma* sagt aus, dass es nicht möglich ist den Grad der Dezentralität (DoD), die Skalierbarkeit und die Sicherheit eines Blockchain Systems gleichzeitig zu maximieren [5; 6; 7]. Daher müssen Software Architekten Kompromisse zwischen DoD, Skalierbarkeit und Sicherheit eingehen, um die nicht-funktionalen Anforderungen für ihren Anwendungsfall zu erfüllen [5]. Es ist schwierig einzuschätzen, wie sich das *Blockchain Trilemma* in einem konkreten Blockchain System manifestiert, bevor es deployed wurde. Es ist teuer und aufwändig für jede Iteration ein reales Blockchain System aufzusetzen [8]. Daher ist ein Tool nötig, das Software Architekten hilft zu verstehen wie sich unterschiedliche Konfigurationen von Blockchain Systemen auf die Manifestation des Blockchain Trilemmas auswirken. Simulationen bieten einen kostengünstigen und ressourcenarmen Ansatz, um große Blockchain Systeme zu untersuchen [3; 8]. Diese Thesis präsentiert 3SIM, ein flexibler, auf Software Architektur fokussierter, Blockchain Simulator zur Untersuchung des Blockchain Trilemmas.

3SIM ist ein *Discrete-Event Simulator*, der ein Meta-Modell und ein stochastisches Simulationsmodell umfasst. Das Meta-Modell von 3SIM erlaubt es Konfigurationen von Blockchain Systemen mit Fokus auf Software Architektur zu modellieren. 3SIM kann als Eclipse-Plugin ausgeführt werden. 3SIM baut auf SM-SIM auf, einem Blockchain Simulator für die Simulation von Selfish-Mining-Attacken [8]. 3SIM errechnet mehrere Ausgabemetriken, die geeignet sind um DoD, Skalierbarkeit und Sicherheit eines simulierten Blockchain Systems einzuschätzen [5].

Experimente werden durchgeführt um die Plausibilität und Nützlichkeit der von 3SIM produzierten Ergebnisse zu demonstrieren. In jedem Experiment wird ein gewisser Eingabeparameter variiert, während die anderen Eingabeparameter fix sind, wie in einer gemeinsamen Grundkonfiguration festgelegt. Somit kann der Einfluss des variierten Eingabeparameters auf die Manifestation des Blockchain Trilemmas untersucht werden. Die variierten Eingabeparameter sind: *mean block creation interval* (\bar{I}_B), also die durchschnittliche Zeitspanne zwischen der Erstellung zweier Blöcke, die *maximale Blockgröße* B_{\max} , *Durchsatz und Latenz* von Links zwischen Validating-Nodes, die Anzahl benötigter *security confirmations* $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, d.h. die benötigte Anzahl an Folgeblöcken, damit ein Block als *confirmed* betrachtet werden kann, und die *Verteilung von Hashing-Power* zwischen den Validating-Nodes.

Die durchgeführten Experimente zeigen, dass sich die Skalierbarkeit eines Blockchain Systems mit längerem \bar{I}_B und weniger *number of required security confirmations* ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$) verbessert. Sehr kurze und sehr lange \bar{I}_B wirken sich negativ auf die Skalierbarkeit aus. Ein

längeres \bar{I}_B verbessert die Sicherheit eines Blockchain Systems mit Blick auf Availability, aber verschlechtert die Consistency, was eine inhärente Abwägung ist [5]. Ein schnelleres P2P-Netzwerk verbessert die Skalierbarkeit und Sicherheit. *degree of decentralization* (DoD) verbessert sich, wenn die Hashing-Power gleichmäßiger auf die Validating-Nodes verteilt ist und wenn die Validating-Nodes gleichmäßig auf geografische Regionen verteilt sind.

3SIM hilft Software Architekten dabei, besser zu verstehen, wie sich Konfigurationen von Blockchain Systemen auf die Manifestation des Blockchain Trilemmas auswirken, und hilft ihnen schnell und iterativ zu untersuchen wie das Blockchain Trilemma sich in einem konkreten Blockchain System manifestiert, bevor es deployed wurde.

Contents

Abstract	i
Zusammenfassung	iii
1 Introduction	1
2 Background	4
2.1 Blockchain Technology	4
2.2 The Blockchain Trilemma	5
2.2.1 Foundations of the Blockchain Trilemma	5
2.2.2 Constructs and Metrics to Measure the Blockchain Trilemma Sub- concepts	7
2.3 Stochastic Foundations	14
2.3.1 Stochastic Processes	14
2.3.2 Coefficient of Variation	14
2.3.3 Correlation	15
3 Related Work	17
4 Design	19
4.1 Metamodel	19
4.2 Simulation Model	25
4.2.1 Entities	28
4.2.2 Node Behavior	28
4.2.3 Data Gathering and Computation of Results	29
5 Implementation	31
6 Evaluation	34
6.1 Experiment Design	34
6.1.1 BASE Configuration	35
6.1.2 Experiments	37
6.2 Experiment Results	40
7 Discussion	87
7.1 Principal Findings	87
7.2 Contributions to Practice	88
7.3 Contributions to Research	88

Contents

7.4	Limitations	88
7.5	Future Research	89
8	Conclusion	90
	Acronyms	91
	Bibliography	93
A	Appendix	99
A.1	Experiment Results Charts Summary	99
A.2	Pairwise Pearson Correlations	110

List of Figures

2.1	Blockchain Trilemma Organigram [5]	6
4.1	Class diagram for <i>blockchain system</i> view type.	19
4.2	Class diagram for <i>repository</i> view type.	20
4.3	Class diagram for <i>node system</i> view type.	20
4.4	Class diagram for <i>node environment</i> sub-view type.	21
4.5	Class diagram for <i>node allocation</i> view type.	21
4.6	Class diagram for <i>link allocation</i> sub-view type.	22
4.7	Class diagram for <i>P2P network</i> sub-view type.	23
4.8	Class diagram for <i>geographical regions</i> sub-view type.	24
4.9	Class diagram for <i>transactions</i> sub-view type.	24
4.10	Communication between validating nodes in block and transaction propagation [8].	28
6.1	Overview of RING topology.	37
6.2	H for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.	43
6.3	H for different <i>mean block creation interval</i> (\overline{I}_B).	44
6.4	H for different <i>maximum block size</i> (B_{\max}).	45
6.5	H for configurations with different throughput and latency.	45
6.6	H for different <i>number of required security confirmations</i> ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$).	46
6.7	HHI_{norm} for different \overline{I}_B .	47
6.8	HHI_{norm} for different B_{\max} .	48
6.9	HHI_{norm} for configurations with different throughput and latency.	49
6.10	HHI_{norm} for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.	50
6.11	HHI_{norm} for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.	50
6.12	$Gini$ for different \overline{I}_B .	51
6.13	$Gini$ for different B_{\max} .	52
6.14	$Gini$ for configurations with different throughput and latency.	53
6.15	$Gini$ for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.	54
6.16	$Gini$ for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.	54
6.17	A_{Sca} for different \overline{I}_B .	55
6.18	A_{Sca} for different B_{\max} .	56
6.19	A_{Sca} for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.	57
6.20	A_{Sca} for configurations with different throughput and latency.	58
6.21	A_{Sca} for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.	58
6.22	TPS for different \overline{I}_B .	59
6.23	TPS for different B_{\max} .	60

6.24	TPS for configurations with different throughput and latency.	61
6.25	TPS for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes. . .	62
6.26	TPS for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	62
6.27	A_{Sec} for different \bar{I}_B	63
6.28	A_{Sec} for different B_{max}	64
6.29	A_{Sec} for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes. .	65
6.30	A_{Sca} for configurations with different throughput and latency.	66
6.31	A_{Sca} for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	67
6.32	Cons for different \bar{I}_B	68
6.33	Cons for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	68
6.34	Cons for different B_{max}	69
6.35	Cons for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.	70
6.36	Cons for configurations with different throughput and latency.	70
6.37	FT for different \bar{I}_B	72
6.38	FT for different B_{max}	73
6.39	FT for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes. . .	74
6.40	FT for configurations with different throughput and latency.	75
6.41	FT for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	75
6.42	R for different \bar{I}_B	76
6.43	R for different B_{max}	77
6.44	R for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes. . .	78
6.45	R for configurations with different throughput and latency.	79
6.46	R for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	79
6.47	SBR for different \bar{I}_B	80
6.48	SBR for different B_{max}	81
6.49	SBR for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes. .	82
6.50	SBR for configurations with different throughput and latency.	82
6.51	SBR for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	83
A.1	Results of the experiment varying \bar{I}_B for each output metric. Part I.	100
A.2	Results of the experiment varying \bar{I}_B for each output metric. Part II. . . .	101
A.3	Results of the experiment varying B_{max} for each output metric. Part I. . .	102
A.4	Results of the experiment varying B_{max} for each output metric. Part II. . .	103
A.5	Results of the experiment with different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes, for each output metric. Part I.	104
A.6	Results of the experiment with different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes, for each output metric. Part II.	105
A.7	Results of the experiment with different throughput and latency of links between validating nodes, for each output metric. Part I.	106
A.8	Results of the experiment with different throughput and latency of links between validating nodes, for each output metric. Part II.	107
A.9	Results of the experiment varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for each output metric. Part I.	108

A.10 Results of the experiment varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for each output metric.
Part II. 109

List of Tables

2.1	Constructs and metrics to operationalize the constructs for measuring the blockchain trilemma subconcepts (i.e., <i>degree of decentralization</i> (DoD), scalability, and security)	8
3.1	Related Blockchain Simulators	18
6.1	Block validation duration probability distribution in BASE configuration . .	35
6.2	Transaction properties in the BASE configuration	35
6.3	Link allocation LA_B in the BASE configuration	36
6.4	Node allocations in the BASE configuration	36
6.5	Link allocation LA_C	38
6.6	Link allocation LA_S	38
6.7	Node allocations for the configurations D1, D3, D4, D5	39
6.8	Pearson correlation ρ between <i>mean block creation interval</i> (\bar{I}_B) and output variables, and corresponding p -value, for 1000 rounds.	40
6.9	Pearson correlation ρ between <i>maximum block size</i> (B_{\max}) and output variables, and corresponding p -value, for 1000 rounds.	41
6.10	GD and NC for configurations D1 to D5 for NET and RING topology.	41
6.11	CV of H for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	43
6.12	CV of H when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.	44
6.13	CV of H when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	44
6.14	CV of H for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	45
6.15	CV of H when varying <i>number of required security confirmations</i> ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$) for 500 and 1000 rounds.	46
6.16	CV of HHI_{norm} when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.	47
6.17	CV of HHI_{norm} when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	48
6.18	CV of HHI_{norm} for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	49
6.19	CV of HHI_{norm} when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds. .	50
6.20	CV of HHI_{norm} for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	51
6.21	CV of $Gini$ when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.	52
6.22	CV of $Gini$ when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	53
6.23	CV of $Gini$ for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	53

List of Tables

6.24	CV of <i>Gini</i> when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds. . . .	53
6.25	CV of <i>Gini</i> for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	54
6.26	CV of A_{Sca} when varying $\overline{I_B}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	55
6.27	CV of A_{Sca} when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	56
6.28	CV of A_{Sca} for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	56
6.29	CV of A_{Sca} for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	57
6.30	CV of A_{Sca} when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds. . . .	58
6.31	CV of <i>TPS</i> when varying $\overline{I_B}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	60
6.32	CV of <i>TPS</i> when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	61
6.33	CV of <i>TPS</i> for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	61
6.34	CV of <i>TPS</i> for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	62
6.35	CV of <i>TPS</i> when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds. . . .	63
6.36	CV of A_{Sec} when varying $\overline{I_B}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	64
6.37	CV of A_{Sec} when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	65
6.38	CV of A_{Sec} for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	65
6.39	CV of A_{Sec} for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	66
6.40	CV of A_{Sec} when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds. . . .	66
6.41	CV of <i>Cons</i> when varying $\overline{I_B}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	68
6.42	CV of <i>Cons</i> when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds. . . .	69
6.43	CV of <i>Cons</i> when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	69
6.44	CV of <i>Cons</i> for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	70
6.45	CV of <i>Cons</i> for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	71
6.46	CV of <i>FT</i> when varying $\overline{I_B}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	71
6.47	CV of <i>FT</i> when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	73
6.48	CV of <i>FT</i> for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	73
6.49	CV of <i>FT</i> for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	74
6.50	CV of <i>FT</i> when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	76
6.51	CV of <i>R</i> when varying $\overline{I_B}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	77
6.52	CV of <i>R</i> when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	78
6.53	CV of <i>R</i> for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	78
6.54	CV of <i>R</i> for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	78

6.55	CV of R when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	79
6.56	CV of SBR when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.	80
6.57	CV of SBR when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.	81
6.58	CV of SBR for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	82
6.59	CV of SBR for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.	83
6.60	CV of SBR when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.	83
6.61	Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiments $\{ex_{P,t,1000} P \in \{\bar{I}_B, B_{\text{max}}\}, t \in \{\text{NET}, \text{RING}\}\}$ while controlling for \bar{I}_B , \bar{I}_B and the topology.	84
6.62	Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table 6.61.	84
A.1	Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{\bar{I}_B, \text{NET}, 1000}$ while controlling for \bar{I}_B	110
A.2	Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.1.	110
A.3	Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{B_{\text{max}}, \text{NET}, 1000}$ while controlling for B_{max}	111
A.4	Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.3.	111
A.5	Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{\bar{I}_B, \text{RING}, 1000}$ while controlling for \bar{I}_B	111
A.6	Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.5.	112
A.7	Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{B_{\text{max}}, \text{RING}, 1000}$ while controlling for B_{max}	112
A.8	Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.7.	112

1 Introduction

Nowadays, blockchain systems are becoming increasingly popular and are used to develop applications in various domains, e.g. finance, health care and internet of things [1; 2; 3; 4]. Each use-case a blockchain system serves, imposes distinct non-functional requirements that it must meet [1; 2; 3; 4]. Key requirements typically include *degree of decentralization* (DoD), *scalability*, and *security*. However, according to the *blockchain trilemma*, the subconcepts DoD, scalability, and security cannot be maximized simultaneously [5; 6; 7]. Software architects must identify Pareto-optimal configurations of blockchain systems to balance the trade-offs between the subconcepts of the blockchain trilemma in order to meet the non-functional requirements for their use case [5]. Therefore, software architects must understand how blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma [5]. Due to the various trade-offs and interdependencies between constructs of the blockchain trilemma [1; 2; 5; 9], it is not obvious how the blockchain trilemma manifests in a concrete blockchain system, before deploying it.

There are various approaches to gather data for the investigation of the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma [5]. The data can be obtained from real-world blockchain systems, but it is difficult to monitor the behavior of large-scale blockchain systems, like Bitcoin [8]. Private test networks allow more control over the blockchain system configuration, e.g. over the block size and network topology [8]. However, benchmarking private test networks is resource-intensive [8]. Therefore, it is costly to benchmark large-scale blockchain systems, and in-depth analyses are limited to only a few blockchain system configurations [8]. *Emulations* can accurately imitate an actual system under controllable conditions [3]. However, running emulations requires significant computational overhead and an emulation is bound to the clock of the emulated system [3]. To overcome these shortcomings, simulations offer a resource-efficient approach to investigate large-scale blockchain systems [3; 8]. Using simulations, software architects can quickly change the modeled blockchain system configuration and observe its influence on the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma, without the effort needed to deploy a real-world blockchain system for each iteration [8]. Simulations allow to quickly gather the necessary data to investigate the influence of different blockchain system configurations on the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma.

Several blockchain simulators were proposed to simulate blockchain systems with PoW-based consensus mechanisms. Each blockchain simulator has its own distinct goals and focus and thus expects different inputs (i.e. its own distinct meta-model) and outputs different data. To gather all relevant data for investigating the influence of blockchain system configurations on the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma, one would have to run several blockchain simulators, i.e. one would have to create a different model of the blockchain system for

each simulator and each iteration. Furthermore, existing blockchain simulators fall short in flexibility of configuring blockchain systems on a software-architecture level [8].

To help software architects gain a better understanding of how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma and identify Pareto-optimal blockchain system configurations to meet their non-functional requirements, a more flexible and software-architecture-focused simulation tool is needed.

I approach the following research questions:

RQ 1 *What is a design of a flexible simulation tool that helps software architects better understand how blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma?*

RQ 2 *How do different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma?*

In this thesis, I present 3SIM, a blockchain simulator for investigating the blockchain trilemma.

I approach the research question in the following steps: I extract common metrics used for estimating the blockchain trilemma subconcepts from Aliyu et al. [5]. In particular, I scrutinize the input variables of these metrics that must be filled with data generated by 3SIM to estimate the blockchain trilemma subconcepts. Using the identified input, I develop a metamodel and simulation model for 3SIM. The metamodel and simulation model build on those of SM-SIM [8]. Using the metamodel of 3SIM, I create concrete models of various blockchain system configurations and run 3SIM on those models. I use the obtained results to investigate how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. Finally, I demonstrate the plausibility and utility of 3SIM.

The meta model of 3SIM, enables modelling blockchain systems on an software-architecture level. The metamodel of 3SIM offers the view types *repository*, *node system*, *blockchain system*, and *deployment*, with the sub-view types *node environment*, *node allocation*, *P2P network*, *geographical regions*, *link allocation*, and *transactions* [8].

The simulation model of 3SIM, enables the use of models developed using the metamodel of 3SIM, to run flexible simulations with different configurations.

By presenting 3SIM, I contribute a novel simulation tool, which helps practitioners to balance the trade-offs imposed by the blockchain trilemma, in order to find blockchain system configurations that meet their non-functional requirements, without the need to deploy a blockchain system for each iteration.

By presenting the results of running 3SIM on various models, I help researchers to gain a better understanding of how different blockchain trilemma metrics are correlated, and how blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma.

In the following chapters, I first introduce foundations of blockchain technology and the blockchain trilemma. I introduce a few basics of stochastics. Next, I discuss existing blockchain simulators and related work. In the next chapters, I introduce the metamodel and simulation model of 3SIM, and I discuss the implementation of 3SIM. Next, I present the design and results of the conducted experiments and evaluate the results produced by 3SIM. In the following chapter, I discuss principal findings, contributions to research and to practice, as well as limitations of 3SIM and possible future work. Finally, I summarize the findings of this thesis in the conclusion.

2 Background

In this section, technical and theoretical foundations are introduced. First I introduce what a blockchain system is and how it works. Next, I introduce the *blockchain trilemma*. Finally, a few statistical foundations are introduced.

2.1 Blockchain Technology

A *blockchain* is a data structure, that stores transactions batched into blocks. Blocks are linked via hash values of correspondingly preceding blocks, forming a chronologically ordered chain of blocks. A *blockchain system* is a type of distributed ledger system, that uses a blockchain to maintain an append-only transcript of records.

In the Bitcoin blockchain system [10], each *block* includes a *block header* and a merkle-patricia tree with *transactions* [4]. The block header contains the *hash value of the previous block*, a *nonce*, and the *hash value of the current block* [4]. It is easy to compute a hash, but it is almost impossible to reconstruct the original data from a hash value [11]. Because the hash value of the previous block is included when hashing its successor block, an attacker would have to modify the hash codes of all blocks in the chain, to modify a block [4].

Blockchains are replicated across multiple validating nodes, i.e. each validating node maintains a local copy of the blockchain [2; 11]. Validating nodes communicate in a peer-to-peer network and synchronize using a *consensus protocol* to agree on an eventually consistent transaction history [2; 11]. *Consensus protocols* specify message passing and local decision-making at every node [12]. The *longest-chain rule* states that the longest valid hash-chain is the valid transaction history that all validating nodes agree upon.

In Proof-of-Work based consensus protocols, validating nodes must solve a computationally difficult challenge (the so-called *mining challenge*) before adding a new block to the ledger [11]. The validating node that first solves the mining challenge receives a *block reward* [11]. In the Bitcoin system, for example, validating nodes receive BTC as a block reward. Validating nodes broadcast newly created blocks to adjacent validating nodes [11]. Upon receipt of a new block, each validating node validates the block and adds the block to its local replica of the blockchain if it is valid.

The consensus protocol used by the Bitcoin blockchain system is called Nakamoto consensus [10; 11]. Nakamoto consensus is PoW-based and uses the longest-chain rule [10; 11]. In Nakamoto consensus, the mining challenge is to guess a random string, called *nonce*, whose hash value has at least the number of preceding zeros as the defined target [11, p. 282].

The target is dynamically adjusted based on the overall computing power of all validating nodes [11, p. 282], to ensure that a new valid block is produced every n minutes on average, in the case of the *Bitcoin* blockchain system, every 10 minutes. The target is called *mining difficulty*. In this thesis, the time n is called *mean block creation interval* and denoted as \bar{I}_B .

2.2 The Blockchain Trilemma

In the following, I introduce the *blockchain trilemma* and its subconcepts, and I discuss common trade-offs between the subconcepts. Next, I introduce metrics suitable to operationalize the constructs of the blockchain trilemma.

2.2.1 Foundations of the Blockchain Trilemma

The *blockchain trilemma* is a concept, which states that it is impossible to simultaneously maximize the subconcepts *degree of decentralization* (DoD), *scalability*, and *security* [5; 6; 7]. An enhancement in one subconcept comes at the expense of one or both other subconcepts [5; 6; 7].

For a blockchain system, a high **DoD** is important, to ensure that no single user or group of users can tamper with the transaction history [13]. A high DoD removes the need to trust a central authority [13]. However, DoD can be viewed from different perspectives, e.g. it can refer to the geographical diversity or the distribution of mining power among validating nodes [5]. An example for the importance of geographical decentralization: if all validating nodes are located in a single country, the government of said country could take control the behavior of the validating nodes. Another example for the importance of decentralization in terms of mining power: In PoW-based blockchain systems, if a single validating node has more than 50 % mining power, it can control the complete transaction history [5; 14]. To encompass all these perspectives, DoD can be defined as “*the degree to which validating nodes equitably and (quasi-)autonomously contribute to consensus finding in a blockchain system* [5, p. 5].”

The **scalability** of a blockchain system is important to support a large number of nodes and large workloads [6]. For example, if the blockchain system is used to operate a cryptocurrency, a high scalability means that many transactions can be executed quickly. Scalability can be defined as “*the ability of a blockchain system to handle changing amounts (e.g., number of validating nodes and transactions per second) of workloads* [5, p. 5].”

The **security** of a blockchain system, “*refers to the degree to which a blockchain system remains operational and is resilient against faults, network partitions, and malicious attacks* [5, p. 5].” For example, an attacker could try to use the same coins to issue multiple transactions, thus spending more coins than the attacker owns (double-spending attack) [8; 14]. Another example is, that validating nodes could selectively withhold mined blocks to set other

validating nodes at a disadvantage (selfish-mining) [8; 14]. It is important that a blockchain system is secure, i.e. resilient against such attacks.

Therefore, software architects aim to optimize the DoD, scalability and security of their blockchain system. However, due to the blockchain trilemma, they must make trade-offs [5; 6; 7]. For example, in health-care high security and scalability might be more important than DoD, whereas in finance security and DoD might be more important than scalability.

Blockchain trilemma subconcepts have dimensions referred to as *constructs* and metrics are used to operationalize these constructs [5]. A metric is a mathematically defined assignment of input variables to output variables [5].

Figure 2.1 shows the relationship of the blockchain trilemma concept, its subconcepts, corresponding constructs, and metrics that operationalize the constructs.

Figure 2.1: Blockchain Trilemma Organigram [5]

In the following, I discuss trade-offs between the subconcepts of the blockchain trilemma.

Trade-offs between DoD and Scalability

In PoW-based blockchain systems, a longer *block creation interval* decreases the frequency of *block reward* payouts [2]. Therefore, validating nodes might join *mining pools*, which decreases the *DoD* of the blockchain system [2].

Trade-offs between Scalability and Security

While shorter *block creation intervals* allow transactions to be added to the distributed ledger faster, validating nodes may not be aware of newly created blocks fast enough, which leads to temporary forks and thus an increased *stale block rate* [2]. With an increasing number of forks, the number of tolerable malicious validating nodes decreases [2]. On the other hand, longer *block creation intervals* decrease *throughput* and increase *confirmation latency*, because it takes more time until enough succeeding blocks are appended for a block to be assumed confirmed [2].

A larger block size can increase throughput, because more transactions can be added to a single block [2], i.e. we can handle more transactions per block creation interval. However,

the block size and bandwidth strongly influence the *block propagation delay*. An increased *block propagation delay* leads to a longer state of inconsistency between validating nodes, which increases the *stale block rate* [2].

Highly varying transaction frequency leads to block size variations, which in turn leads to varying block propagation delays that increase the probability of successful selfish-mining attacks [2].

Trade-offs between DoD and Security

In PoW-based blockchain systems, a high DoD is important to ensure the integrity of the stored data [2]. The DoD increases with an increasing amount of nodes participating in consensus finding [2]. The more validating nodes participate in a blockchain system, the more unlikely it is, for them to have the same malicious intentions, which means that 51%-attacks become unlikely [2].

In PoW-based blockchain systems, each validating node performs all computations on its local replica of the blockchain [2]. Therefore, with an increasing number of validating nodes the total amount of computational effort in the blockchain system increases while the average transaction rate is constant [2]. An incentive mechanism is required, to compensate validating nodes for their computational effort [2]. In case of the Bitcoin blockchain system, transaction issuers have to pay *transaction fees*.

2.2.2 Constructs and Metrics to Measure the Blockchain Trilemma Subconcepts

Table 2.1 lists the constructs that 3SIM simulates. For each construct, the table shows the metric used to operationalize the construct and the input variables required by that metric. 3SIM collects data to fill all the listed input variables and computes the output variables of the listed metrics at the end of each simulation run.

Because 3SIM uses probabilistic simulation methods, a Monte Carlo Simulation can be performed, wherein 3SIM calculates the (converging) average value of each metric's output variable over n simulation rounds.

In the following, each construct listed in table 2.1 is briefly introduced.

2.2.2.1 Degree of Decentralization (DoD)

This section presents metrics suitable to investigate the DoD of a blockchain system.

Block Proposal Randomness (Shannon Entropy H) *Block Proposal Randomness* is a construct of the DoD subconcept, which describes “[t]he degree to which it is uncertain what validating node will propose the next block [5, p. 11].”

The *Shannon Entropy* is a suitable metric for the *Block Proposal Randomness*, and denoted as H [5]. A higher H indicates, an even participation of validating nodes in consensus finding and thus a high DoD, and vice versa [5].

H is defined as [5]:

$$H = -k \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{b_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n b_j} \log_2 \left(\frac{b_i}{\sum_{i=j}^n b_j} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

Wherein n refers to the *total number of validating nodes* and b_i refers to the *total number of blocks proposed* by the i -th validating node [5].

Geographical Diversity *Geographical Diversity* describes “[t]he degree to which validating nodes in a blockchain system are distributed across different locations [5, p. 11].” The geographical diversity construct can be operationalized with the metric of the same name, *Geographical Diversity*, denoted as GD and defined as follows [5]:

$$GD = \frac{(GD_{\text{excl}} - GD_{\text{target}}) - GD_{\text{equal}}}{GD_{\text{excl}} - GD_{\text{equal}}} \quad (2.2)$$

The auxiliary geographical diversity GD_{aux} is used to calculate GD [5]:

$$GD_{\text{aux}} = \left(2 - \frac{\log_{(|N|+1)} |N_t| - \log_{(|N_t|+1)} |N_t|}{\log_2 |N_t| - \log_{(|N_t|+1)} |N_t|} \right) \times \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{|N_t|} (|n_i| - \frac{n}{|N_t|})^2}{|N_t|}} \quad (2.3)$$

Here $|N_t|$ is the total number of regions, $|N|$ is the number of regions where validating nodes operate, $|n_i|$ is the number of validating nodes that operate in the i -th region, and n is the total number of validating nodes [5]. GD_{excl} is the GD_{aux} if all validating nodes of a blockchain system were operated in one region, GD_{equal} is the GD_{aux} if all nodes were distributed equally across regions, and GD_{target} is the actual GD_{aux} of the blockchain system to be quantified [5].

Hashing Power Distribution (Nakamoto Coefficient NC) The *Hashing Power Distribution* is a construct of the DoD subconcept, that describes “[t]he extent to which hashing power is distributed among all validating nodes that compete to propose the next block [5, p. 14].” The *Nakamoto Coefficient NC* is a suitable metric to operationalize the *Hashing Power Distribution* [5]. “Nakamoto coefficient is the minimum number of validating nodes needed to surpass a threshold in hashing power required to control a blockchain system [5, p. 14].” A high NC means that attackers must gain control over a relatively large number of validating nodes to control consensus finding, which indicates a high DoD, and vice versa [5].

NC is defined as follows [5]:

$$NC = \min_{k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}} \sum_{i=1}^k p_i \geq t \quad (2.4)$$

Whereas p_i is the hashing power of the i -th validating node [5]. In PoW-based blockchain systems, attackers must control more than 50% of validating nodes to control the consensus finding [5]. Therefore, $t = 0.5 * \sum_{i=1}^n p_i$ is commonly used as a threshold for calculating NC of PoW-based blockchain systems.

Token Concentration (Herfindahl-Hirschman-Index HHI) The *Token Concentration* is a construct of the DoD subconcept, that describes the “distribution of token shares that validating nodes own in a blockchain system [5, p. 11].”

A suitable metric for the token concentration is the *Herfindahl-Hirschman-Index HHI* [5]. A high HHI indicates that most tokens are owned by a small subset of validating nodes, which suggest that not all validating nodes have the same chance to win the *block reward*, i.e. not all validating nodes are equally successful in participating in the consensus finding [5]. Therefore, a high HHI indicates low DoD, and vice-versa [5].

For better comparability across configurations with a different number of validating nodes n , the *normalized Herfindahl-Hirschman-Index HHI_{norm}* can be used, which is independent of n [5].

HHI and HHI_{norm} are defined as follows [5]:

$$HHI = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{t_i}{t_{\text{total}}} \right)^2 \quad (2.5)$$

$$HHI_{\text{norm}} = \frac{n}{n-1} HHI - \frac{1}{n-1}$$

Wherein t_i is the amount of tokens owned by the i^{th} validating node and $t_{\text{total}} = \sum_{j=1}^n t_j$ [5].

Wealth Distribution (Gini Coefficient $Gini$) *Wealth Distribution* is a construct of the DoD subconcept, which describes the “degree of inequality between validating nodes in terms of token ownership [5, p. 11].” The *Gini Coefficient*, denoted as $Gini$, is a suitable metric for *Wealth Distribution* [5]. $Gini \in [0, 1]$ holds, whereas $Gini = 0$ indicates equal wealth distribution among validating nodes, and $Gini = 1$ indicates high inequality in wealth distribution [5].

$Gini$ is defined as follows [5]:

$$Gini = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |t_i - t_j|}{2 \times n} \quad (2.6)$$

Whereas n is the total number of validating nodes and t_i the number of tokens owned by the i^{th} validating node [5].

2.2.2.2 Scalability

This section presents metrics suitable to investigate the scalability of a blockchain system.

Availability (A_{Sca}) Availability is a construct of the scalability subconcept that describes the “degree to which a blockchain system is operational and delivers up-to-date responses [5, p. 11].” A suitable metric for the availability regarding scalability is A_{Sca} , which is defined as follows [5]:

$$A_{Sca} = \frac{NumberOfConfirmedTransactions}{NumberOfIssuedTransactions} \times 100\% \quad (2.7)$$

Low availability means slower synchronization of validating nodes, which can lead to network partitions in blockchain systems with partial availability, such as the Bitcoin blockchain system [5]. Thus, a high A_{Sca} is an indicator of high security [5].

Confirmation Latency *Confirmation Latency* is a construct of the Scalability subconcept, that describes the “timespan between the proposal of new blocks and their confirmation [5, p. 11].” The metric CL is suitable to operationalize confirmation latency [5].

CL is defined as follows [5]:

$$CL = BlockConfirmationTime - BlockProposalTime \quad (2.8)$$

Where $BlockProposalTime$ is the timestamp when a new block is proposed, and $BlockConfirmationTime$ is the timestamp when the block is confirmed [5]. Since the block creation interval can vary between consecutive blocks [5], 3SIM calculates the mean of all confirmation latencies that occurred in the simulation run, denoted as \overline{CL} . Because \overline{CL} is equivalent to the *Cons* metric of the security subconcept, 3SIM only outputs *Cons*.

Transaction Throughput (TPS) *Transaction throughput* refers to “the highest number of transactions a blockchain system can process in a specified timeframe [5, p. 11].” The metric *transactions per second*, denoted as *TPS*, is suitable to operationalize the transaction throughput [5].

TPS is defined as follows [5]:

$$TPS = \frac{\text{NumberOfConfirmedTransactions}}{t_1 - t_0} \quad (2.9)$$

Where $[t_0; t_1]$ is the observation timeframe for which *TPS* is calculated [5].

2.2.2.3 Security

This section presents metrics suitable to investigate the security of a blockchain system.

Availability (A_{Sec}) Availability regarding security refers to “[t]he degree to which a blockchain system operates correctly at an arbitrary time [5, p. 11].” A_{Sec} is a suitable metric for the availability construct regarding security [5], and is defined as follows [5]:

$$A_{Sec} = \frac{\text{MeanTimeBetweenFailures}}{\text{MeanTimeBetweenFailures} + \text{MeanTimeToRepair}} \times 100\% \quad (2.10)$$

$$\text{MeanTimeBetweenFailures} = \frac{\text{TotalOperationalTime}}{\text{NumberOfFailures}} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\text{MeanTimeToRepair} = \frac{\text{TotalRepairTime}}{\text{NumberOfRepairs}} \quad (2.12)$$

Blockchain systems can be unoperational for various reasons and it is not clear what type of failure should be considered when calculating A_{Sec} , which can make the metric less meaningful [5].

Consistency *Consistency* refers to “[t]he degree to which all validating nodes are in a shared and agreed-upon state [5, p. 11].” The metric *Cons* is suitable to operationalize the consistency construct, and is defined as follows [5]:

$$Cons = \frac{1}{n_{\text{security_confirmation}}} \times \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{security_confirmation}}} (\text{BlockConfirmationTime}_i - \text{BlockProposalTime}_i) \quad (2.13)$$

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ is the number of required security confirmations, $\text{BlockProposalTime}_i$ is the system time when a new valid block b_i is issued to the blockchain system,

BlockConfirmationTime_{*i*} is the system time when the block b_i is confirmed [5]. b_i is considered confirmed, if it is in the longest chain and has $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ succeeding blocks [5].

Fault Tolerance FT The *fault tolerance* refers to “[t]he degree to which a blockchain system operates correctly despite experiencing accidental or Byzantine faults [5, p. 11].” The fault tolerance regarding performance changes denoted as FT is a suitable metric for the fault tolerance construct [5].

FT is defined as [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} FT &= \{\Delta TPS, \Delta CL\} \\ \Delta TPS &= |TPS|_N - |TPS|_F \\ \Delta CL &= |CL|_N - |CL|_F \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Whereas $|TPS|_N$ and $|CL|_N$ denote the TPS and CL when the blockchain system is operating normally, and $|TPS|_F$ and $|CL|_F$ denote the TPS and CL when the blockchain system is faulty [5]. However, similar to A_{Sec} , blockchain systems can be unoperational for various reasons and it is not clear what type of failure should be considered when calculating FT , which can make FT less meaningful [5].

Reliability R *Reliability* is a construct of the security subconcept that describes “[t]he continuity of a blockchain system to offer correct service [5, p. 11].” The reliability $R(t)$ is a suitable metric for the reliability construct, and defined as follows:

$$R(t) = e \left(-\frac{t}{\text{MeanTimeBetweenFailures}} \right) \quad (2.15)$$

$R(t)$ denotes the probability that a blockchain system may not operate reliably within the timeframe t [5]. However, similar to A_{Sec} and FT , blockchain systems can be unoperational for various reasons and it is not clear what type of failure should be considered when calculating $R(t)$, which can make $R(t)$ less meaningful [5].

Stale Block Rate SBR In blockchain systems with probabilistic finality, if validating nodes propose blocks simultaneously only the fastest propagating block is accepted into the main chain, while the other blocks become stale [5]. The stale block rate describes the number of stale blocks in a specified timespan [5]. The metric with the same name, denoted as SBR , is defined as follows [5]:

$$SBR = \frac{\text{NumberOfStaleBlocks}}{\text{NumberOfConfirmedBlocks}} \quad (2.16)$$

2.3 Stochastic Foundations

In this section several stochastic foundations are introduced.

2.3.1 Stochastic Processes

In the following, I define several stochastic processes that are used in the simulation model of 3SIM.

Definition 1 (Point process) *A point process is a stochastic process with a series of random variables that represent the arrival times of an event, and can be denoted as $\{t_n; n \geq 0\}$, where t_n is the arrival time of the n -th event (n -th arrival time) and $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_n < \dots$ [15].*

Definition 2 (Interarrival time) *For the point process $\{t_n; n \geq 0\}$ where t_n is the n -th arrival time, the n -th interarrival time is $X_n = t_n - t_{n-1}$ [15]. Note that $t_n = \sum_1^n X_n$ [15].*

Definition 3 (Counting process) *A counting process is a stochastic process with a series of random variables that represent the number of events in a given time interval, and can be denoted as $\{N(t); t \geq 0\}$, where $N(t)$ is the number of events in time interval $(0, t]$ [15].*

Definition 4 (Renewal process) *A renewal process is a counting process in which the interarrival times X_n are independent and identically distributed random variables [15].*

Definition 5 (Poisson process) *A Poisson process is a renewal process in which the interarrival times $\{X_n; n \geq 1\}$ are independent exponential random variables with the same rate λ [15].*

2.3.2 Coefficient of Variation

Definition 6 (Coefficient of Variation CV) *Assume a series of n numbers, called sample. Let σ be the standard deviation of the sample, and let μ be the mean of the sample. The CV of the sample is defined as $CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu}$ [8; 16].*

The CV measures the variability of the sample independently of the used unit of measurement [16].

2.3.3 Correlation

For all definitions in this section,

- let X and Y be two random variables,
- let μ_X be the mean of X ,
- let μ_Y be the mean of Y ,
- let σ_X be the standard deviation of X ,
- let σ_Y be the standard deviation of Y .

Definition 7 (Covariance cov) *The covariance of X and Y is defined as $\text{cov}(X, Y) = \mathbf{E}[XY] - \mu_X\mu_Y$, where $\mathbf{E}[XY]$ is the expected value of the product of X and Y [17].*

Definition 8 (Pearson Correlation Coefficient ρ) *The Pearson correlation coefficient of X and Y is defined as $\rho_{X,Y} = \frac{\text{cov}(X,Y)}{\sigma_X\sigma_Y}$ [18].*

The Pearson correlation coefficient indicates how strongly two variables are linearly related, whereas $\rho = -1$ indicates a perfectly negative linear relation, $\rho = 1$ indicates a perfectly positive linear relation and $\rho = 0$ indicates that there is no linear relation between the two variables [19].

Partial correlation is the correlation between two variables X and Y , after the effect of a third so-called *control variable* Z is removed [19].

Definition 9 (Partial Pearson Correlation Coefficient) *Let X and Y be two random variables and let Z be the control variable. The partial Pearson correlation coefficient of X and Y while controlling for Z is defined as [19]:*

$$\rho_{XY|Z} = \frac{\rho_{XY} - \rho_{XZ}\rho_{YZ}}{[(1 - \rho_{XZ}^2)(1 - \rho_{YZ}^2)]^{1/2}} \quad (2.17)$$

Next, let me define the t -statistic and introduce the p -value.

Definition 10 t -statistic For a sample of n values $X = x_1 \dots x_n$, let \bar{x} be the mean of the sample, let μ denote the expected mean, and let σ be the standard deviation of the sample. The t -statistic is defined as [20]:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}} \quad (2.18)$$

To test if the pearson correlation coefficient ρ of a sample is statistically significant, a p -value can be calculated [20]. Let the null hypothesis be $\{H_0 : \rho = 0\}$. Using a t -statistic the p -value can be obtained from a table or using statistical software [20]. If the p -value is below a threshold α , H_0 can be rejected, suggesting that ρ is statistically significant [20]. In this thesis the commonly used threshold $\alpha = 0.05$ is used.

3 Related Work

Several blockchain simulators were proposed to simulate PoW-based blockchain systems, enabling collection of data on different blockchain trilemma subconcepts. Each blockchain simulator has its own distinct goals and focus, and thus blockchain simulators take different input parameters and produce different outputs.

Based on existing systematic reviews of existing blockchain simulators [21; 22] and based on further literature research, I consolidated a list of blockchain simulators that can simulate PoW-based blockchain systems, presented in table 3.1. For each blockchain simulator, table 3.1 shows the input variables (of metrics listed in table 2.1) that can be filled with data gathered by that blockchain simulator.

Table 3.1 shows that most input variables of the metrics listed in table 2.1 are simulated by at least one of the listed blockchain simulators, but none of them can provide data to fill all the input variables.

Common variables like *block creation interval* and *average block proposal time* are simulated by most blockchain simulators.

10 of the 27 listed blockchain simulators simulate the geographical distribution of validating nodes, but none of the listed blockchain simulators allows specifying all regions available in the simulated world (the *total number of geographical regions*). 4 of the 27 listed blockchain simulators produce data regarding the block confirmation, whereas only the *Local Bitcoin Network* [39] blockchain simulator simulates the *average block confirmation time*.

Only 2 of the 27 listed blockchain simulators produce data for the *operational time* of the simulated blockchain system. Not all blockchain simulators simulate transactions, some only simulate blocks. 3SIM can combine the learnings from the listed blockchain simulators, to be able to produce data for all input variables of the metrics listed in table 2.1.

Even if there was a subset of existing blockchain simulators that in summary would provide all the data necessary to compute the output metrics listed in table 2.1, one would have to model the same blockchain system configuration with a different metamodel for each of those blockchain simulators, which is tedious.

Simulator	Language	Extends	Block creation interval	Average block proposal time	Number of required security confirmations	Average block confirmation time	Hashing power per validating node	Total number of nodes	Number of validating nodes	Number of confirmed blocks	Number of mined blocks	Number of generated blocks	Number of orphan blocks	Total number of regions	Region per validating node	Number of issued transactions	Number of confirmed transactions	Operational time / Number of failures and repairs	Average block propagation delay	Average transaction propagation delay	Maximum block size	Transaction fee	Mining reward
Behavior and Quality of Blockchain [23]	Python		✓													✓							
Bitcoin Mining Vulnerability [24]																							
BlockEval [25]	Python		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓	✓	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]
BlockPerf [26]	Python	BlockSim	✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]
BlockSim (Alharby) [27]	Python		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]
BlockSim (Faria) [28]	Python		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]
BlockSIM (Pandey) [29]	Python		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]
BlockSim-Net [30]	Python	BlockSim	✓	✓			✓	✓				✓ [22]	✓		✓						✓ [22]		
BSELA [31]			✓	✓			✓	✓					✓										
CBlockSim [32]	C	BlockSim	✓	✓			✓	✓					✓										
ChainSim [33]	Python	BlockSim	✓	✓				✓															
Data-driven Analysis [34]		BlockSim	✓	✓			✓	✓															
Difficulty Adjustment With SimBlock [35]		SimBlock	✓	✓			✓	✓															
eVIBES [36]	Scala	VIBES	✓	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓	✓							✓ [22]
Ext 2 - simBlock [37]	Java	SimBlock	✓	✓			✓	✓							✓								
Ext-simblock [38]	Java	SimBlock	✓	✓			✓	✓							✓								
Local Bitcoin Network [39]	Python		✓			✓	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]							✓ [22]				
LUNES [40]								✓															
Modeling by Queuing Theory [41]	Java	SimBlock	✓	✓			✓	✓															
Security and Performance of PoW [14]			✓	✓			✓	✓															
Shadow-Bitcoin [42]	Python		✓	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓					✓ [22]		✓ [22]
SIMBA [43]	Python	BlockSim	✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓					✓ [22]		
SimBlock [44]	Java		✓ [22]	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]		✓ [22]	✓					✓ [22]		✓ [22]
SW-SIM [8]	Java		✓	✓			✓	✓															
Superhashing Power Dilemma [45]			✓	✓			✓	✓															
User Privacy Simulator [46]			✓	✓			✓	✓															
VIBES [47]	Scala		✓	✓			✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]			✓				✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]	✓ [22]
3SIM	Kotlin, Java		✓	✓			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓						✓		✓

Table 3.1: Related Blockchain Simulators

4 Design

3SIM comprises a metamodel and a simulation model. The metamodel offers the foundational concepts to derive blockchain system models with a focus on software architectures. The simulation model defines the dynamics in blockchain system models, enabling the execution of blockchain system simulations.

3SIM extends SM-SIM, a discrete-event simulator for blockchain systems using proof-of-work consensus with the longest chain fork resolution rule [8]. SM-SIM presents a software-architecture focused metamodel to derive blockchain system models, based on the *Palladio Component Model (PCM)* [8]. PCM is a general metamodel to represent component-based software architectures [8; 48]. 3SIM extends the metamodel of SM-SIM and introduces a simulation model. Using the simulation model of 3SIM, one can investigate how the blockchain trilemma manifests in a concrete blockchain system modelled using the metamodel of 3SIM. The metamodel and simulation model are introduced in the following sections.

4.1 Metamodel

In model-driven software engineering, to analyze a system, a single, consistent *model* of the system is created, whereas the model is an instance of its *metamodel* [49]. To show parts of the model, concrete syntaxes defined by *view types* are used. A *view type* defines the objects and relationships that a *view* of the respective type can contain [49]. A *view* is a concrete instance of a *view type* with the actual set of objects and their relations [49].

The metamodel of 3SIM offers the view types *repository*, *node system*, *blockchain system*, and *deployment*. These view types are interconnected and collectively define the structure and behavior of a blockchain system [8; 48].

Figure 4.1: Class diagram for *blockchain system* view type.

The *blockchain system* view type describes a full blockchain system [8]. The `BlockchainSystem` is the root model element [8], which contains a `BlockchainSystemSpecification` and references a `P2PNetwork`, a `GeographicalRegionsSpecification`, and a `TransactionsSpecification`.

The BlockchainSystemSpecification defines attributes to specify the *mean block creation interval* (\bar{I}_B), the *maximum block size* (B_{\max}), the *block reward* R_B and the *number of required security confirmations* ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$), i.e. the number of succeeding blocks needed for a block to be considered confirmed. Figure 4.1 shows the class diagram of the *blockchain system view type*.

Figure 4.2: Class diagram for *repository view type*.

Figure 4.3: Class diagram for *node system view type*.

The *repository* view type of the metamodel of SM-SIM was adopted in the metamodel of 3SIM unchanged [8]. The *repository* view type defines the component type BlockchainSystemNodeComponent, that represents the functionalities of nodes in a blockchain system [8]. The BlockchainSystemNodeComponent comprises a MiningProcessComponent and BlockValidatorComponent [8]. The MiningProcessComponent represents a component that participates in the mining challenge to produce blocks, and allows to differentiate between validating and non-validating nodes [8]. The BlockValidatorComponent represents a component that implements the validation of blocks a node receives from adjacent nodes [8]. Figure 4.2 shows the class diagram for the *repository* view type.

The *node system* view type of the metamodel of SM-SIM was adopted in the metamodel of 3SIM unchanged [8]. The *node system* view type describes which BlockchainSystemNodeComponents are assembled on a blockchain system node [8]. Figure 4.3 shows the class diagram for the *node system* view type.

The *deployment view type* describes how the blockchain system will be deployed [8], and it has the sub-view types *node environment*, *node allocation*, *P2P network* [8], *geographical regions*, *link allocation*, and *transactions*.

Figure 4.4: Class diagram for *node environment* sub-view type.

Figure 4.5: Class diagram for *node allocation* view type.

The *node environment* sub-view type was adopted from the metamodel of SM-SIM unchanged [8]. Figure 4.4 shows the class diagram of the *node environment* sub-view type.

In the *node allocation* sub-view type, the NodeAllocation was extended to have a reference to a GeographicalRegion, which allows specifying the geographical region in which a node is deployed. Figure 4.5 shows the class diagram of the *node allocation* sub-view type.

Figure 4.6: Class diagram for *link allocation* sub-view type.

The metamodel of 3SIM introduces a new *link allocation* sub-view type, that describes the transmission properties of links between nodes in the P2P network. A LinkAllocation contains a LinkLatencySpecification and a LinkThroughputSpecification.

LinkLatencySpecification is an abstract class, implemented by StaticLinkLatencySpecification, which can be used to specify a static latency for the link, and DynamicLinkLatencySpecification which can specify a link with fluctuating latency. The DynamicLinkLatencySpecification specifies a list of DynamicLinkLatencySpecificationValues, each specifying a *latency* in ms, a *probability* of the link having that latency, and a *duration* for which the latency is applicable. Similarly, the LinkThroughputSpecification is an abstract class implemented by StaticLinkThroughputSpecification, which can be used to specify a static throughput for the link, and DynamicLinkThroughputSpecification which can specify a link with fluctuating throughput. The DynamicLinkThroughputSpecification specifies a list of DynamicLinkThroughputSpecificationValues, each specifying a *throughput* in $\frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}}$, a *probability* of the link having that throughput, and a *duration* for which the throughput is applicable. The LinkAllocationRepository represents a collection of reusable link allocation definitions. Figure 4.6 shows the class diagram of the *link allocation* sub-view type.

The *P2P network* sub-view type describes the topology of the P2P network of a blockchain system, specifying the position of nodes and the links between them [8]. A P2PNetwork contains a NetworkTopology, which represents the structure of the P2P network [8]. NetworkTopology is an abstract class implemented by ExplicitNetworkTopology and ConnectedSubgraphsNetworkTopology. An ExplicitNetworkTopology contains Nodes, each referencing a NodeAllocation, and Links. A Link is an abstract class that is implemented by UnidirectionalLink and BidirectionalLink. Each Link has a reference to a LinkAllocation.

Figure 4.7: Class diagram for *P2P network* sub-view type.

A `UnidirectionalLink` can be used to specify a unidirectional link between two `Nodes`, referenced via the additional attributes `fromNode` and `toNode`. This allows simulating different inbound and outbound traffic for links between nodes. A `BidirectionalLink` has references to two `Nodes`. A `ConnectedSubgraphsNetworkTopology` represents a network topology consisting of connected subgraphs. The `ConnectedSubgraphsNetworkTopology` can contain multiple `SubgraphSpecifications` and `SubgraphLinks` between subgraphs. A `SubgraphLink` references a `LinkAllocation` and has references to the two `SubgraphSpecifications` it connects. A `SubgraphSpecification` specifies a connectivity of the nodes within the subgraph, references a `LinkAllocation` to use for all links between nodes in the subgraph, and can contain multiple `SubgraphNodeTemplates`. A `SubgraphNodeTemplate` references a `NodeAllocation` that is used for nodes created from this template, and specifies the number of nodes that shall be created from this template in the subgraph and whether nodes of this template are subgraph proxies (connecting two subgraphs). Figure 4.7 shows the class diagram of the *P2P network* sub-view type.

The *geographical regions* sub-view type describes the geographical regions that exist in the world, i.e. that nodes can possibly be in. The `GeographicalRegionsSpecification` is

Figure 4.8: Class diagram for *geographical regions* sub-view type.

Figure 4.9: Class diagram for *transactions* sub-view type.

a collection of `GeographicalRegions`, each identified by a unique region name. Figure 4.8 shows the class diagram of the *geographical regions* sub-view type.

The *transactions* sub-view type describes the properties of transactions submitted to the blockchain system and the frequency at which they are submitted. The `TransactionsSpecification` specifies the *mean transaction creation interval* ($\overline{I_{\text{trx}}}$) and contains a `TransactionPropertiesSpecification`. The `TransactionPropertiesSpecification` is a list of `TransactionPropertiesSpecificationValues`, each specifying a *size* of the transaction in B, a *fee* in tokens \otimes and a *probability* of a transaction with these properties being submitted to the blockchain system. Figure 4.9 shows the class diagram of the *transactions* sub-view type.

4.2 Simulation Model

3SIM uses a discrete-event simulation model.

System state is a function of time $S(t)$ that returns a collection of variables containing all information necessary to describe the simulated system at any point in time t [50]. The current simulation time t_c is stored in a global variable `CLOCK` [8; 50]. In discrete-event simulation models, system state only changes at discrete points in time called *event times* [50]. The system state at an event time t_e is called *snapshot* $S(t_e)$ [50]. A discrete-event simulation progresses from snapshot to snapshot [50].

Let an event be represented by (e_i, t_o) , where e_i is the type of the event and t_o is the time of its occurrence [8]. A so-called *future event list* (*FEL*) is a list of events chronologically ordered by their occurrence time t_o [8; 50]. At any given simulation time, the events that will occur at a known, definite future simulation time, are stored in the *FEL* [50]. The event stored in *FEL* with the smallest event time is called the *imminent event*, which is the next event to occur [50].

In 3SIM, the simulation process starts by adding initial events to the *FEL*, with `generateInitialEvents()` [8]. A loop runs as long as $|FEL| > 0$ and the termination conditions checked by `shouldTerminate()` are not met. In each iteration of the loop, the events with occurrence time $t_o = \text{CLOCK}$ are removed from *FEL* and `onEventsOccured(events)` processes these events and schedules new events by adding them to *FEL*, finally `advanceClock()` advances the `CLOCK` to the occurrence time of the imminent event, before continuing with the next iteration of the loop. The event processing loop algorithm is outlined in algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Event Processing Loop

```

1 Function RunSimulation
2   generateInitialEvents()
3   while  $|FEL| > 0 \wedge \neg \text{shouldTerminate}()$  do
4      $t \leftarrow \text{getCurrentTime}()$ 
5     events  $\leftarrow \text{popEventsAt}(FEL, t)$ 
6     onEventsOccured(events)
7     advanceClock()
8   end
9   determineResults()
10 end

```

In 3SIM, `shouldTerminate()` stops the simulation once a node has a blockchain of at least length x , whereas x can be specified by the user. `generateInitialEvents()` generates a *block mined event* for each blockchain system node.

The `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` is a `SimulationMonitor` that continuously observes the system state.

The smallest possible time slice in 3SIM is a millisecond [ms], i.e. `CLOCK` is a *Long* storing the current simulation time in ms.

An event e is scheduled by adding it to the *FEL*, i.e. $FEL = FEL \cup \{e\}$ [8].

The process of producing new blocks is referred to as the *mining process* in 3SIM [8]. The simulation model of 3SIM assumes a constant mining difficulty [8]. In the Bitcoin blockchain system, realistic interarrival times of blocks are exponentially distributed [8; 51], therefore 3SIM uses a Poisson process $\{N_B(t); t \geq 0\}$ to schedule *block mined events*. The *mean block creation interval* \bar{I}_B is an input variable to the simulation, i.e. for all $n \geq 1$ the expected interarrival time of *block mined events* $E[X_n]$ shall equal \bar{I}_B . Therefore, $E[X_n] = \frac{1}{\lambda} \stackrel{!}{=} \bar{I}_B \implies \lambda = \frac{1}{\bar{I}_B}$, and consequently $E[N(t)] = \lambda * t = \frac{1}{\bar{I}_B} * t$. Let $g(\lambda)$ be a generator function, that returns an exponentially distributed value with rate λ [8]. When a validating node starts the *mining process* a *block mined event* $e_{\text{block_mined}} = (\text{block_mined}, \text{CLOCK} + g(\bar{I}_B))$ is scheduled [8]. The transactions included in the block are selected from the *transaction mempool* of the validating node proposing the block, by selecting the transactions with the best *fee-rate* $\frac{\text{transaction_fee}}{\text{transaction_size}}$ as long as the size of the selected transactions does not exceed B_{max} , which is an input to the simulation. The transaction selection is outlined in algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: Selection of transactions to be included in a block

```

1 Function SelectTransactions
2   currentBlockSize  $\leftarrow$  0
3   transactions  $\leftarrow$  {}
4   while currentBlockSize <  $B_{\text{max}}$  do
5     transaction  $\leftarrow$  transactionMemPool.pop()
6     /* transactionMemPool.pop() returns and removes the transaction with
7       the highest fee-rate: transaction.fee / transaction.size */
8     transactions.push(transaction)
9   end
10  return transactions
11 end

```

Once a validating node receives a new block from an adjacent validating node, the validating node validates the block hash and transactions batched in the block [8]. The simulation takes a user-defined probability distribution $D_{\text{block_validation}}$ as an input parameter, whereas $X_{\text{block_validation}} \sim D_{\text{block_validation}}$ is a random variable denoting *block validation durations*. Once a validating node receives a new block from an adjacent node, a *block validation duration* $d_{\text{block_validation}}$ is drawn from $X_{\text{block_validation}}$ and a new event $e_{\text{block_validated}} = (\text{block_validated}, \text{CLOCK} + d_{\text{block_validation}})$ is scheduled.

3SIM does not simulate *transaction originators*, e.g. wallets of users that submit transactions to the blockchain system, instead transactions are sent from anonymous transaction origins. The \bar{I}_{trx} is an input parameter to the simulation. Similarly to the *mining process* 3SIM uses a Poisson process $\{N_B(t); t \geq 0\}$ with rate $\lambda = \frac{1}{\bar{I}_{\text{trx}}}$ to schedule *transaction submitted events*. A set of tuples $(p_i, \text{fee}_i, \text{size}_i)$ is an input to the simulation, where fee_i is a transaction fee in

tokens, $size_i$ is the transaction size in byte and p_i is a probability, whereas $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$ must hold. Let X_T be a random variable taking values $(1, 2, \dots, n)$ with $P(X_T = i) = p_i$. Once the simulation starts, an event $e_{\text{transaction_submitted}} = (\text{transaction_submitted}, \text{CLOCK} + g(\overline{I_{\text{trx}}}))$ is scheduled. For each *transaction submitted event* a validating node to receive the transaction is randomly chosen and properties (fee, size) for the transaction are drawn from X_T . The randomly chose node that the transaction was submitted to, adds the transaction to its *transaction mem-pool* and starts propagating the transaction to its adjacent nodes, via the *transmission protocol*.

Nodes in the *P2P* network that are connected with a link can communicate by sending each other messages. Let $L_{a,b}$ be a link from a node a to a node b . Let $l_{L_{a,b}}(t)$ be the latency of link $L_{a,b}$ at time t and $tp_{L_{a,b}}(t)$ the throughput of link $L_{a,b}$ at time t . The transmission duration t_m is the time it takes for the message m to be sent from a to b via $L_{a,b}$, which is calculated as $t_m = l_{L_{a,b}}(t) + \text{size_of}(m)/tp_{L_{a,b}}(t)$. Links can either have a static latency or dynamic latency and either have a static throughput or dynamic throughput. For links with static latency $l_{L_{a,b}}(t) \equiv l_{L_{a,b}}$, where $l_{L_{a,b}}$ is an input to the simulation model, and analogous for static throughput. For links with dynamic latency, the simulation model takes probability distribution $D_{L_{a,b}}$ as an input parameter. Let $X_{L_{a,b}} \sim D_{L_{a,b}}$ be a random variable denoting a pair (l, d) , where l is the latency and d the duration for which the latency is applicable. For a dynamic link $L_{a,b}$ a call to $l_{L_{a,b}}(t)$ draws a new pair (l, d) from $X_{L_{a,b}}$ if no latency is cached, and then caches l until $c = \text{CLOCK} + d$. If $l_{L_{a,b}}(t)$ is called before c ($t \leq c$) then the cached latency l is returned, else a new pair is drawn. $tp_{L_{a,b}}(t)$ is computed analogously. An example for how the latency of a link is cached is outlined in algorithm 3, which works analogously for the throughput of links.

Algorithm 3: Selection of a latency for a link over time

```

1 Function LinkLatencySelection
2   if  $\text{CLOCK} < \text{latencyValidUntilTimestamp}$  then
3     return cachedLatency
4   else
5     latencyObject  $\leftarrow$  draw based on user defined probability distribution
6     cachedLatency  $\leftarrow$  latencyObject.latency
7     latencyValidUntilTimestamp  $\leftarrow$   $\text{CLOCK} + \text{latencyObject.duration}$ 
8   end
9 end

```

The *transmission protocol* describes how *blocks* and *transactions* are transmitted to another node [8]. The transmission protocol uses three types of messages: *inv_message*, *get_data_message* and *data_message* [8]. If a node a wants to transmit a *block* or *transaction* to another node b , a first sends an *inv_message* to b containing the unique *hash of the block* or *transaction id* respectively. When b receives the *inv_message* it checks if a block with the received hash exists in its blockchain or whether the transaction with the received id exists in its transaction mem-pool, if so the communication is done, otherwise b sends a *get_data_message* to a to request the *block* or *transaction*. Once a receives a *get_data_message*

it responds with a *data_message* containing the requested *block* or *transaction*. Figure 4.10 illustrates a block transmission between two nodes [8].

Figure 4.10: Communication between validating nodes in block and transaction propagation [8].

4.2.1 Entities

In discrete-event simulation models, an entity is any component of the system which requires explicit representation in the simulation model [50]. 3SIM uses the following entities:

Blockchain is an *entity* of the simulation model, which represents the local blockchain data structure maintained on a node [8].

Stale block pool is an *entity* of the simulation model, which stores blocks that arrive out of order [8].

Transaction mempool is an *entity* of the simulation model, which, for each node, stores the transactions that the node received but that are not yet included in a block.

4.2.2 Node Behavior

In 3SIM only honest nodes are simulated. Once a validating node produced a block, it triggers a *BlockMinedEvent*, adds the block to its local blockchain [8] and removes all transactions included in the block from its *transaction mempool*. Validating nodes multicast each transaction that was submitted to them, and each validated and produced block to their adjacent nodes via the *transmission protocol* [8]. When a validating node receives a transaction, it adds the transaction to its *transaction mempool*, if not already included. When a validating node receives a new block, a *BlockReceivedEvent* is scheduled by the *transmission protocol* [8]. After a validating node has validated a block, it schedules a *BlockValidatedEvent* [8]. If a validating node has the required previous block, the newly validated block is added to the local blockchain of the validating node [8], and all transactions included in the block are removed from the *transaction mempool* of the validating node. If the validating node does not have the previous block, it stores the block in its *stale block pool* [8].

4.2.3 Data Gathering and Computation of Results

In discrete-event simulators, data required to estimate the system quality measures of interest, is gathered by observing the simulated system over the course of the simulation [50].

So-called `TraceEvents` are emitted by 3SIM at certain points in the simulation. `TraceEvents` can be logged to the console, a file or a database. 3SIM uses a `SimulationMonitor` that listens to `TraceEvents`, to observe the simulated system over the course of the simulation and gather necessary data to produce the simulation output.

Once the `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` observes a `TransactionSubmittedTraceEvent` a counter `numberOfSubmittedTransactions` is incremented.

When a validating node produces a new block, a `BlockMinedTraceEvent` is emitted. The `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` keeps a map `blocksProposedPerNode` with ids of validating nodes as key and integer values. Once the `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` observes a `BlockMinedTraceEvent` it increases the value of `blocksProposedPerNode` for the node that proposed the block.

The `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` has for each block type (included, confirmed, stale and forked) a map that associates the block to a list of validating nodes that have this block in their local blockchain replica. Once a validating node adds a block to its local blockchain replica, a `BlockAppendedTraceEvent` is emitted. Once a block changes its type in the local blockchain replica of any validating node, e.g. from included to confirmed, a `BlockTypeChangedTraceEvent` is emitted. When the `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` observes a `BlockAppendedTraceEvent` or a `BlockTypeChangedTraceEvent`, it tracks in the corresponding map (based on block type) that the validating node that emitted the event has the block in its local blockchain replica. A block is considered valid, if at least 50% of validating nodes have the block in their local blockchain replica. Once the `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` observes a `BlockAppendedTraceEvent`, it also checks if the local blockchain of the validating node that emitted the trace event has reached the maximum length, specified as an input to the simulation, and if so, stops the simulation.

If the `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` observes a `BlockAppendedTraceEvent` or a `BlockTypeChangedTraceEvent` and the block is a confirmed block (has at least the number of succeeding blocks specified by the `numberOfRequiredSecurityConfirmations` input parameter to the simulation), the transaction throughput since the last confirmed block is calculated. If the throughput falls below the `failureThroughputThreshold` specified as an input parameter to the simulation, the system is considered failed. `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` keeps a `failureLog` that tracks when a failure occurred and how long it lasted. If a failure is encountered, a failure start is logged in the `failureLog` and the *transaction throughput* and *confirmation latency* encountered during the failure are logged. If the transaction throughput increases again above the `failureThroughputThreshold`, the end of the failure is logged in the `failureLog`, which calculates the duration of the failure (from failure-started timestamp to failure-ended timestamp).

Once the simulation round is finished, the `ThreesimSimulationMonitor` computes a final state, based on the data collected during the simulation run. The final state is stored in the `ThreesimSimulationMonitorState` class, which is outlined in listing 4.1. The data encompassed by the `ThreesimSimulationMonitorState` suffices to calculate all output metrics listed in table 2.1.

```
class ThreesimSimulationMonitorState(
    val numberOfNodes: Int,
    val hashPowerPerNode: Collection<Double>,
    val blocksProposedPerNode: Collection<Int>,
    val numberOfGeographicalRegions: Int,
    val numberOfNodesPerRegion: Collection<Int>,
    val numberOfSubmittedTransactions: Int,
    val numberOfConfirmedTransactions: Int,
    val tokensHeldPerNode: List<Double>,
    val blockProposalTimeAndConfirmationTimePerConfirmedBlock: Collection<Pair<Long, Long>>,
    val meanTimeBetweenFailures: Double,
    val meanTimeToRepair: Double,
    val numberOfStaleBlocks: Int,
    val numberOfConfirmedBlocks: Int,
    val averageThroughputDuringFailure: Double,
    val averageThroughputDuringNormalOperation: Double,
    val averageConfirmationLatencyDuringFailure: Double,
    val averageConfirmationLatencyDuringNormalOperation: Double
)
```

Listing 4.1: `ThreesimSimulationMonitorState` is a class that stores all data gathered during a 3SIM simulation run.

For Monte-Carlo simulations with n rounds, the average of each output metric over all n rounds, is also calculated and provided as an output.

5 Implementation

3SIM extends SM-SIM [8] and Palladio [48]. **Palladio** is an Eclipse plugin written in *Java*. Simulation tools that build upon Palladio, like SM-SIM and 3SIM, are also developed as Eclipse plugins.

While SM-SIM was written in *Java*, 3SIM is mostly written in **Kotlin**. Kotlin is a modern programming language, that targets the *Java Virtual Machine (JVM)* [52]. Kotlin and Java code is fully interoperable and can safely coexist in the same application [52]. A main design guideline for Kotlin is a better handling of null values [52]. Research shows that using Kotlin has no negative effect on the maintainability of applications, helps to write more concise code and reduces the frequency of `NullPointerExceptions` [52]. The parts of source code of SM-SIM that needed to be changed for 3SIM were ported to Kotlin, while other (unchanged) Java classes from SM-SIM are used directly in 3SIM.

3SIM uses **Eclipse EMF**, “a modeling framework and code generation facility for building tools [...] based on a structured data model [53].” The metamodel of 3SIM is implemented as an *Ecore* model. A *GenModel* takes the *Ecore* model and generates *Java* code that *a)* represents the metamodel of 3SIM with Java classes, and *b)* provides a graphical editor, that lets users create models using the metamodel of 3SIM.

Maven Tycho enables building Eclipse plug-ins, features and update sites using *Maven* [54]. 3SIM uses Maven Tycho to build the Eclipse plugins it encompasses, build features into which the plugins are grouped and build an update site, that can be used to install these features.

The code base of 3SIM is structured into the following **packages**:

- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.plugin`: Common base Eclipse plugin for Palladio-based blockchain simulators.
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.core`: Common logic and abstractions for Palladio-based blockchain simulators.
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.loggers`: Loggers to log trace events of the blockchain simulation to console, file, or database.
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.bscm`: Ecore-based metamodel for the 3SIM blockchain simulator.

- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.threesim_plugin`: The entry point of the 3SIM Eclipse plugin. Contains the `LaunchConfiguration` to run 3SIM simulations as launches in Eclipse.
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.threesim`: The business logic for the 3SIM blockchain simulator.
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.kotlin-deps`: Provides the `kotlin-stdlib`, `kotlinx.serialization` and `kotlinx.coroutines` libraries as OSGi bundles. Allows executing plugins written in Kotlin in Eclipse.
- `releng`
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.target_platform`: Target platform definition for the 3SIM Eclipse plugin. The target platform file is automatically merged with the Palladio target platform file.
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.update-site`: Builds an update site that can be used to install the 3SIM Eclipse plugin.
- `features`: Contains features that can be installed via the update site.

The 3SIM update site provides the following four **features**:

- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.feature.bscm`: A feature that contains the metamodel of 3SIM. It provides the following packages:
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.bscm`
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.bscm.edit` (*generated with EMF*)
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.bscm.editor` (*generated with EMF*)
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.feature.kotlin-deps`: A feature that provides the `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.kotlin-deps` package, to enable running plugins written in Kotlin in Eclipse.
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.feature.core`: A feature that contains the core logic and abstractions for Palladio-based blockchain simulators. It includes the packages:
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.core`
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.loggers`
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.plugin`
- `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.feature.threesim`: A feature to install 3SIM. It contains the packages:
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.threesim`
 - `org.palladiosimulator.blockchainsystems.threesim_plugin`

These features facility code reuse. Eclipse plugins written in Kotlin can reuse the `kotlin-deps` feature. Possible future Palladio-based blockchain simulators can reuse common logic and abstractions from the `core` feature, and can reuse the metamodel of 3SIM with the `bscm` feature.

A **code review** was conducted to ensure good code quality and that the intended goals are met.

6 Evaluation

Several experiments are conducted to demonstrate the plausibility of results produced by 3SIM and to show the utility of 3SIM. Because 3SIM uses a stochastic simulation model, all experiments are conducted as Monte-Carlo experiments with 500 and 1000 rounds.

The result of a 3SIM Monte-Carlo simulation run contains for each simulation round a set with values for all output metrics listed in table 2.1, and for each output metric its average over all rounds. I compare the average result values for each output metric to existing research on said output metric, in order to demonstrate the plausibility and consistency of these result values.

Based on the results of the conducted experiments, I examine how different blockchain system configurations affect each produced output metric value, in order to demonstrate the utility of 3SIM.

Furthermore, based on the simulation results, I analyze how the output metrics that 3SIM produces are correlated to each other.

In the following, the experimental design is outlined, and the experiment results are presented.

6.1 Experiment Design

All experiments are conducted on two different network topologies, namely NET and RING. For each topology a BASE configuration is constructed. In each experiment some parameter is varied, while the other input parameters remain unchanged, as specified in the BASE configuration.

Because 3SIM uses a stochastic simulation model, each experiment is conducted as a Monte-Carlo experiment with multiple simulation rounds. In each experiment and for each variation, 500 and 1000 simulation rounds are executed. In each simulation round the blockchain system is simulated until the longest chain in the local blockchain replica of any validating node reaches a length of 35 blocks.

For the NET topology, 3SIM generates a new network configuration based on the specified topology in each round, in order to reduce bias from individual network configurations. For the RING topology, the same explicitly specified network configuration is used for each round.

In the following, I describe the BASE configuration and how each experiment varies the configuration.

6.1.1 BASE Configuration

The BASE configuration has a *maximum block size* $B_{\max} = 1$ MB and a *mean block creation interval* $\bar{I}_B = 10$ min. The *required number of security confirmations* is set to $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 6$. All simulated nodes are validating nodes participating in the mining process. The block rewards and transaction fees are specified in an arbitrary unit referred to as “tokens” and denoted as \otimes . The *block reward* is set to $B_{\text{reward}} = 6000.00 \otimes$. For each block that needs to be validated, the *block validation duration* is drawn from the probability distribution specified in table 6.1.

Probability [%]	$d_{\text{block_validation}}$ [s]
50	5
40	10
10	15

Table 6.1: Block validation duration probability distribution in BASE configuration

In the simulated world there are 3 available geographical regions where validating nodes can be located—for simplicity we call these regions ASIA, EUROPE, and NORTH AMERICA.

The *mean transaction creation interval* (\bar{I}_{trx}) is set to $\bar{I}_{\text{trx}} = 100$ ms, i.e., a new transaction is submitted to a random validating node every 100 ms. Newly submitted transactions have a size in byte [B] and fee in tokens [\otimes] selected based on the probabilities specified in table 6.2.

Probability [%]	Size [B]	Fee [\otimes]
30	250	0.01
20	500	0.02
10	500	0.03
20	750	0.03
10	750	0.04
10	1000	0.04

Table 6.2: Transaction properties in the BASE configuration

In 3SIM, similar links between validating nodes, i.e. links that share the same latency and throughput characteristics, can be created from a template called *link allocation*. All links between validating nodes in the P2P network in the BASE configuration share the *link allocation* presented in table 6.3, referred to as LA_B . The LA_B specifies an expected latency of $E[LA_B \text{ latency}] = 100$ ms and an expected throughput of $E[LA_B \text{ throughput}] = 80\,060.6061 \frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}} \approx 10 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}}$.

Latency Specification			Throughput Specification		
Probability [%]	Latency [ms]	Duration [s]	Probability [%]	Throughput [$\frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}}$]	Duration [s]
0.2	110	1000	0.5	82 000	4000
0.6	100	3000	0.3	78 000	3000
0.2	95	2000	0.2	75 000	2000

Table 6.3: Link allocation LA_B in the BASE configuration

Node Allocation No.	Hashing Power [$\frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$]	Geographical Region
1	80	NORTH AMERICA
2	80	ASIA
3	100	EUROPE
4	130	ASIA
5	130	EUROPE
6	150	ASIA
7	160	NORTH AMERICA
8	200	EUROPE

Table 6.4: Node allocations in the BASE configuration

The BASE configuration has 8 *node allocations*, with the hashing powers and geographical regions specified in table 6.4.

The P2P network of the NET topology in the BASE configuration uses the `ConnectedSubgraphsNetworkTopology`, containing a *single subgraph specification* with a *connectivity* of 4, i.e., each validating node in the subgraph is connected to 4 other validating nodes. All links between validating nodes within the subgraphs use the link allocation LA_B . The subgraph specification contains 8 node templates, whereas each node template uses one of the node allocations listed in table 6.4 and produces 4 validating nodes with that node allocation. Therefore, the P2P network of the NET topology in the BASE configuration, contains 32 validating nodes in total, whereas 12 validating nodes are in Europe, 12 validating nodes are in Asia and 8 validating nodes are in North America. Furthermore, the P2P network of the NET topology in the BASE configuration has a total hashing power of 4120 MH.

The P2P network of the RING topology in the BASE configuration uses the `ExplicitNetworkTopology`, to explicitly arrange 16 validating nodes in a bidirectional ring. All links between validating nodes in the ring use link allocation LA_B . Each node allocation listed in table 6.4 was randomly assigned to 2 validating nodes in the ring. The position of each validating node in the ring can be found in section 6.1.1.

Figure 6.1: Overview of RING topology.

Circles represent validating nodes, the number prefixed with N inside the circle represents the number of the node allocation from table 6.4 that is assigned to the validating node.

6.1.2 Experiments

To demonstrate the plausibility of the results produced by 3SIM, I varied several parameters while keeping the other parameters as specified in the BASE configuration and I then examined how the varied parameter influences the results for each output metric. The varied parameters are *mean block creation interval* (\bar{I}_B), *maximum block size* (B_{\max}), *throughput and latency of links between validating nodes*, *number of required security confirmations* ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$), and *distribution of hashing power among validating nodes*.

In the following, let a *simulation run* $\text{sim}_{p,t,r}(p)$ be a run of 3SIM for topology $t \in T = \{\text{NET}, \text{RING}\}$, and number of rounds $r \in R = \{500, 1000\}$, where the input parameter P is set to $p \in P$. An experiment is a set of one simulation run for each discrete value p that the input parameter P was varied to, denoted as $\text{ex}_{t,r,P} = \{\text{sim}_{p,t,r}(p) \mid p \in P\}$.

For the \bar{I}_B , I simulated the values 20 s, 1 min, 2.5 min and 10 min (= BASE configuration). For the B_{\max} I simulated the values 75 kB, 250 kB, 500 kB, 1 MB (= BASE configuration), 2 MB, 4 MB and 8 MB.

In the experiment, where throughput and latency of links was varied, three different configurations were used: *Total Crashes* (C), *Slow* (S), BASE. In configuration C all links between validating nodes in both topologies use a new link allocation LA_C , which is presented in table 6.5. LA_C specifies a 10 % chance of a link failing completely (throughput = 0) for 1 s, but $\mathbf{E}[LA_C \text{ latency}] = 100 \text{ ms} = \mathbf{E}[LA_B \text{ latency}]$ and $\mathbf{E}[LA_C \text{ throughput}] = 79\,939.3939 \frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}} \approx 10 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}} = \mathbf{E}[LA_B \text{ throughput}]$. In configuration S all links between validating nodes in both

topologies, use a new link allocation LA_S , which is presented in table 6.6. LA_S specifies an expected latency of $E[LA_S \text{ latency}] = 200 \text{ ms} = 2 * E[LA_B \text{ latency}]$ and an expected throughput of $E[LA_S \text{ throughput}] = 40\,054.9451 \frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}} \approx 5 \frac{\text{kB}}{\text{s}} \approx \frac{1}{2} * E[LA_B \text{ throughput}]$.

Latency Specification			Throughput Specification		
Probability [%]	Latency [ms]	Duration [s]	Probability [%]	Throughput [$\frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}}$]	Duration [s]
0.2	110	1000	0.5	83 000	4000
0.6	100	3000	0.4	81 500	3000
0.2	95	2000	0.1	0	1000

Table 6.5: Link allocation LA_C

Latency Specification			Throughput Specification		
Probability [%]	Latency [ms]	Duration [s]	Probability [%]	Throughput [$\frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}}$]	Duration [s]
0.4	180	3000	0.3	39 000	4500
0.5	210	6000	0.4	42 000	5000
0.1	170	2000	0.3	38 000	4000

Table 6.6: Link allocation LA_S

In the another experiment, the distribution of hashing power among the validating nodes was varied. 5 configurations were constructed, called D1 to D5, whereas D2 is the BASE configuration, and the other configurations are presented in table 6.7.

Lastly, in one experiment the $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ was varied to 2, 6 (equals BASE configuration), and 10.

For all experiments the failure throughput threshold was set to $f_{\text{threshold}} = 1 \frac{\text{transaction}}{\text{min}}$, i.e. the simulated blockchain system was considered failed, if the transaction throughput fell below $f_{\text{threshold}}$ and considered repaired, once the transaction throughput increased above $f_{\text{threshold}}$ again.

Convergence of results. The *coefficient of variation CV* was used to assess the convergence of simulation results. Let M be the set of output metrics computed by 3SIM, as specified in table 2.1. For each *simulation run* $\text{sim}_{P,t,r}(p)$, the *CV* was calculated for each output metric $m \in M$. Let $CV_{P,t,r}(p, m)$ denote the *CV* for $\text{sim}_{P,t,r}(p)$ and metric m . A decreasing *CV* for an increasing number of simulation rounds suggests convergence of the results [8]. A $CV \leq 0.05$ is desirable [8].

Correlations. For the experiments where the parameters \overline{I}_B and B_{max} were varied, the *pearson correlation coefficient* ρ between the varied parameter and the corresponding average result of each output variable was calculated (except for GD and NC , because these are deterministically calculated from the model and not influenced by \overline{I}_B and B_{max}).

For a simulation run $\text{sim}_{P,t,r}(p)$ let $\text{sim}_{P,t,r}(p, m)$ denote the average simulation run result for metric $m \in M$. Let $\rho_{t,r}(P, m)$ denote the *pearson correlation coefficient* of the sample $\left\{ \left\{ p, \text{sim}_{P,t,r}(p)(m) \right\} \mid p \in P \right\}$.

Node Allocation No.	Hashing Power [$\frac{MH}{s}$]	Geographical Region
D1		
1	50	EUROPE
2	50	ASIA
3	50	NORTH AMERICA
4	50	EUROPE
5	50	ASIA
6	50	NORTH AMERICA
7	50	EUROPE
8	50	ASIA
D3		
1	330	EUROPE
2	240	ASIA
3	60	NORTH AMERICA
4	60	ASIA
5	80	EUROPE
6	90	NORTH AMERICA
7	90	ASIA
8	80	EUROPE
D4		
1	100	EUROPE
2	100	EUROPE
3	100	EUROPE
4	100	ASIA
5	50	EUROPE
6	50	NORTH AMERICA
7	50	NORTH AMERICA
8	50	ASIA
D5		
1	200	EUROPE
2	200	EUROPE
3	50	EUROPE
4	50	EUROPE
5	50	EUROPE
6	50	NORTH AMERICA
7	50	NORTH AMERICA
8	50	ASIA

Table 6.7: Node allocations for the configurations D1, D3, D4, D5

For each $\rho_{t,r}(P, m)$ the corresponding p -value $p_{t,r}(P, m)$ was calculated. The null hypothesis is $\{H_0 : \rho_{t,r}(P, m) = 0\}$. If $p_{t,r}(P, m) < \alpha = 0.05$, $\rho_{t,r}(P, m)$ is called *statistically significant*

and the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. If $0.03 < p_{t,r}(P, m) < 0.07$, the correlation is called *borderline significant* [20].

Furthermore, using the results from the experiments where the parameters \bar{I}_B and B_{\max} were varied, the pairwise *partial pearson correlation* between all output variables (again, except GD and NC) was calculated, controlling for \bar{I}_B and B_{\max} .

6.2 Experiment Results

In the following, I present the results of the conducted experiments for each output metric listed in table 2.1.

Metric	NET		RING	
	ρ	p	ρ	p
A_{Sca}	0.6057	0.3943	0.9728	0.0272
A_{Sec}	0.7869	0.2131	0.8599	0.1401
$Cons$	0.9920	0.0080	0.9615	0.0385
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.6048	0.3952	-0.5667	0.4333
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.9934	0.0066	0.9625	0.0375
$Gini$	-0.9543	0.0457	-0.9893	0.0107
HHI_{norm}	-0.9311	0.0689	-0.9366	0.0634
R	0.9794	0.0206	0.9797	0.0203
H	-0.9751	0.0249	-0.9973	0.0027
SBR	-0.9152	0.0848	-0.9243	0.0757
TPS	0.6059	0.3941	0.9728	0.0272

Table 6.8: Pearson correlation ρ between \bar{I}_B and output variables, and corresponding p -value, for 1000 rounds.

Metric	NET		RING	
	ρ	p	ρ	p
A_{Sca}	0.6051	0.1500	0.0743	0.8742
A_{Sec}	-0.0616	0.8956	0.0263	0.9553
$Cons$	0.8464	0.0163	0.9063	0.0049
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.2078	0.6548	0.7411	0.0567
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.7255	0.0650	0.8184	0.0244
$Gini$	0.8553	0.0141	0.9192	0.0034
HHI_{norm}	0.8665	0.0116	0.9341	0.0021
R	0.3361	0.4611	-0.1847	0.6917
H	0.8176	0.0247	0.8318	0.0203
SBR	0.8528	0.0147	0.9327	0.0022
TPS	0.6052	0.1499	0.0743	0.8742

Table 6.9: Pearson correlation ρ between B_{max} and output variables, and corresponding p -value, for 1000 rounds.

Geographical Diversity GD and Nakamoto Coefficient NC

The Geographical Diversity GD and the Nakamoto Coefficient NC are not subject to stochastic processes in the simulation model, but are deterministically calculated directly from the model.

For all experiments the threshold for NC is set to 50%. GD and NC only change for the experiment configurations D1, D3 to D5, while they remain as in the BASE configuration for all other experiments. Table 6.10 presents the GD and NC for configurations D1 to D5 for both topologies.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	GD [%]	NC [validating nodes]	GD [%]	NC [validating nodes]
D1	≈ 75	16	≈ 75	8
BASE	≈ 75	13	≈ 75	7
D3	50	12	50	6
D4	≈ 75	8	≈ 75	4
D5	≈ 9.8612	7	≈ 9.8612	4

Table 6.10: GD and NC for configurations D1 to D5 for NET and RING topology.

Because GD and NC are calculated deterministically, the plausibility and accuracy of the GD and NC that 3SIM outputs can be proven by verifying the formulas used to calculate GD and NC in the 3SIM source code.

Example. As an example, in the following I show how GD and NC are calculated for the NET topology in the BASE configuration.

In the BASE configuration for the NET topology, there are 32 validating nodes in total, of which 12 validating nodes operate in ASIA, 12 validating nodes operate in EUROPE, and 8 validating nodes operate in NORTH AMERICA. GD can then be calculated as:

$$GD_{\text{excl}} = \left(2 - \frac{\log_2 3 - \log_4 3}{\log_2 3 - \log_4 3}\right) \times \sqrt{\frac{(32 - \frac{32}{3})^2 + (0 - \frac{32}{3})^2 + (0 - \frac{32}{3})^2}{3}} = 1 \times \sqrt{\frac{682.6}{3}} \approx 15.0849$$

$$GD_{\text{equal}} = \left(2 - \frac{\log_4 3 - \log_4 3}{\log_2 3 - \log_4 3}\right) \times \sqrt{\frac{3 * (\frac{32}{3} - \frac{32}{3})^2}{3}} = 0$$

$$GD_{\text{target}} = \left(2 - \frac{\log_4 3 - \log_4 3}{\log_2 3 - \log_4 3}\right) \times \sqrt{\frac{(12 - \frac{32}{3})^2 + (12 - \frac{32}{3})^2 + (8 - \frac{32}{3})^2}{3}} = 2 * \sqrt{\frac{10.6}{3}} \approx 3.7712$$

$$GD \approx \frac{(15.0849 - 3.7712) - 0}{15.0849 - 0} \approx 0.75$$

A $GD = 0.75$ is equally calculated by 3SIM, as presented in table 6.10.

In the BASE configuration for the NET topology, there are 8 validating nodes with hashing power $80 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, 4 validating nodes with hashing power $100 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, 8 validating nodes with hashing power $130 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, 4 validating nodes with hashing power $150 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, 4 validating nodes with hashing power $160 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, and 4 validating nodes with hashing power $200 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$. Therefore, in total the system has a hashing power of $8 * 80 + 4 * 100 + 8 * 130 + 4 * 150 + 4 * 160 + 4 * 200 = 4120 [\frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}]$. The threshold is set to 50 %, i.e. a hashing power of $4120 * 0.5 = 2060$ is needed to control the blockchain system. With the 4 validating nodes with hashing power $200 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, the 4 validating nodes with hashing power $160 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$, the 4 validating nodes with hashing power $150 \frac{\text{MH}}{\text{s}}$ a hashing power of $4 * 150 + 4 * 160 + 4 * 200 = 2040$ is reached with 12 validating nodes. Add any of the remaining validating nodes to reach a hashing power > 2060 . Therefore, at least 13 validating nodes are needed to control the blockchain system. Consequently, $NC = 13$ holds, as calculated by 3SIM (see table 6.10).

Shannon Entropy H

A high Shannon Entropy H suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good *degree of decentralization* (DoD) [5].

In all experiments, the H was consistently higher for the NET topology than the RING topology, suggesting that the simulated blockchain system with the NET topology has a better DoD than with the RING topology, which is plausible and can be explained with the following observation.

Observation 1 Suppose a bidirectional ring of n validating nodes with links $\{\{1, 2\}, \dots, \{n-1, n\}, \{n, 1\}\}$ that all have the same characteristics. Assume validating node 1 proposes a new block. Validating node 1 can propagate the new block in both directions, i.e. to validating nodes n and 2. The last validating node to receive the new block is thus validating node $x = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$. Assume it takes m seconds for the new block to be transmitted via any link, then validating node x receives the new block after $(\lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil - 1) * m$ seconds. In this time x has an inconsistent view of the blockchain, and can thus not participate equally in consensus finding. While in a ring where all validating nodes have equal hashing power, this effect affects all validating nodes equally and thus averages out, it still takes overall longer to reach consensus than e.g. in the NET topology, where validating nodes can propagate new blocks via multiple paths.

Section 6.2 shows that for both topologies, H increases with an increasingly equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, which is plausible, because a more equal distribution of hashing power means that validating nodes have a more equal chance to propose the next block, which leads to a higher H .

Figure 6.2: H for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.0420	0.0411	0.0426	0.0461
D4	0.0400	0.0404	0.0433	0.0445
D3	0.0307	0.0309	0.0289	0.0300
D2/Base	0.0318	0.0313	0.0267	0.0279
D1	0.0285	0.0282	0.0217	0.0224

Table 6.11: CV of H for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Section 6.2 shows that for both topologies, H decreased with an increasing \bar{I}_B . $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong negative correlation between \bar{I}_B and H . The corresponding p -values, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$ are statistically significant.

Figure 6.3: H for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.0201	0.0205	0.0157	0.0162
60	0.0249	0.0250	0.0164	0.0174
150	0.0267	0.0267	0.0185	0.0177
600	0.0318	0.0313	0.0267	0.0279

Table 6.12: CV of H when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Section 6.2 shows that for both topologies, H increased with an increasing B_{\max} . $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, H)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, H)$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate a correlation between B_{\max} and H . The corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.9, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, H)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, H)$ are statistically significant.

B_{\max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.0349	0.0357	0.0368	0.0359
250 kB	0.0328	0.0353	0.0380	0.0362
500 kB	0.0323	0.0317	0.0319	0.0302
1 MB	0.0318	0.0313	0.0267	0.0279
2 MB	0.0296	0.0282	0.0219	0.0206
4 MB	0.0283	0.0272	0.0186	0.0182
8 MB	0.0285	0.0289	0.0199	0.0179

Table 6.13: CV of H when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.4: H for different B_{\max} .

As shown in section 6.2, H remained relatively stable for the different throughput configurations, which is plausible, because bandwidth variations are not reflected in Shannon entropy when focusing on block proposals [5].

Figure 6.5: H for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.0301	0.0311	0.0196	0.0190
S	0.0292	0.0274	0.0248	0.0232
BASE	0.0318	0.0313	0.0267	0.0279

Table 6.14: CV of H for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Furthermore, as shown in section 6.2, for both topologies, H was not affected much by different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, which is plausible, because the chance of a validating node

participating equally in consensus finding is not affected by the number of security confirmations needed for a block to be assumed confirmed.

Figure 6.6: H for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.0307	0.0312	0.0299	0.0274
6	0.0318	0.0313	0.0267	0.0279
10	0.0309	0.0303	0.0277	0.0269

Table 6.15: CV of H when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Tables 6.11 to 6.15, show that the CV for H was always below the threshold of 0.05 in all conducted experiments, for both topologies, for all configurations, and for 500 and 1000 rounds. This suggests a low dispersion of the result values for H , which is desirable.

Normalized Herfindahl-Hirschman Index HHI_{norm}

The normalized Herfindahl-Hirschman Index HHI_{norm} represents the concentration of token ownership by validating nodes [5]. In 3SIM validating nodes can only get tokens by earning *block rewards* and *transaction fees*. In a real-world blockchain system validating nodes can transfer tokens between each other, which makes the HHI_{norm} less meaningful.

A low HHI_{norm} suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good DoD [5].

In all experiments, the HHI_{norm} was consistently lower for the *Net* topology, suggesting that it has a better DoD than the *Ring* topology, which is plausible, and can be explained with observation 1.

Observation 2 *If a validating node has a slow network connection, it needs more time to get a consistent view of the blockchain, i.e. it might spend longer on mining based on an already stale view of the blockchain, and thus have less time for finding the next valid block, which gives it a disadvantage. Validating nodes that participate less equally in consensus finding, receive less block rewards and transaction fees [5]. Therefore, tokens concentrate at fewer validating nodes that are able to get a consistent view of the blockchain faster [5].*

Section 6.2 shows that for both topologies, HHI_{norm} decreased with an increasing \bar{I}_B , which is plausible, because a shorter \bar{I}_B worsens the effect outlined in observation 2, as validating nodes have even less time to get a consistent view of the blockchain. $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, HHI_{\text{norm}})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, HHI_{\text{norm}})$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong negative correlation between \bar{I}_B and HHI_{norm} . However, as shown in table 6.8, the corresponding p -values at $p_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, HHI_{\text{norm}}) \approx 0.0689$ and $p_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, HHI_{\text{norm}}) \approx 0.0634$ suggest that the correlations are only borderline significant.

Figure 6.7: HHI_{norm} for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.7136	0.3404	0.7632	0.7613
60	0.3145	0.4222	0.7096	0.6902
150	0.3392	0.3568	0.6199	0.7994
600	0.2639	0.2790	0.7039	0.8939

Table 6.16: CV of HHI_{norm} when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Larger blocks also take longer to propagate in the network, thus taking longer to reach validating nodes with slow network connections, leaving them with an inconsistent view of the blockchain for longer (observation 2). It is therefore plausible, that for both topologies,

HHI_{norm} increased with an increasing B_{max} (see section 6.2). The effect of B_{max} on HHI_{norm} was even stronger for the RING topology.

As shown in table 6.9, $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, HHI_{\text{norm}})$ indicates a positive correlation between B_{max} and the average HHI_{norm} for the NET topology, and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, HHI_{\text{norm}})$ indicates an even stronger positive correlation between B_{max} and the average HHI_{norm} for the RING topology. For both topologies, the corresponding p -values were below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlations are statistically significant.

Figure 6.8: HHI_{norm} for different B_{max} .

B_{max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.2501	0.2561	0.3464	0.3435
250 kB	0.2585	0.2670	0.4010	0.3729
500 kB	0.2640	0.2814	0.4406	0.4122
1 MB	0.2639	0.2790	0.7039	0.8939
2 MB	0.3382	0.3407	0.8748	0.7611
4 MB	0.3339	0.3097	0.7666	0.6984
8 MB	0.3270	0.3971	0.6384	0.6849

Table 6.17: CV of HHI_{norm} when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

The HHI_{norm} remains stable for different network configurations for the NET topology. For the RING topology, HHI_{norm} decreases drastically from configuration C to S, which suggests that the DoD is worse in a ring with links that can fail than in a ring where all links are slow, but do not fail.

Observation 3 Suppose a bidirectional ring of n validating nodes with links $\{\{1, 2\}, \dots, \{n - 1, n\}, \{n, 1\}\}$. Assume that the link $\{n, 1\}$ between validating nodes 1 and n fails. Validating node 1 can now only propagate messages in one direction. Assume it takes m seconds for a message to be transmitted via a link. It takes $(n - 1) * m$ for the message multicast from

validating node 1 to reach validating node n . Comparing observation 1, one can see that a single failed link can in the worst case double the time it takes for a message to be passed from one validating node to another. Now suppose another link between validating node $x = \lceil \frac{n}{2} \rceil$ and validating node $x - 1$ fails. Now the ring is split into a partition containing validating nodes 1 to $x - 1$ and another partition containing validating nodes x to n , whereas nodes in one partition cannot communicate with nodes in the other partition. Therefore, the validating nodes in each partition now work on their own fork, and global consensus can only be reached once at least one of the failed links is repaired. Without loss of generality, two or more failed links in a bidirectional ring lead to two or more independent partitions of the network.

Observation 3 shows that if links in the ring can fail completely, independent network partitions can be created, which greatly affects DoD, therefore it is plausible that HHI_{norm} decreases drastically from configuration C to S for the RING topology.

Figure 6.9: HHI_{norm} for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.2977	0.2913	1.0515	1.0484
S	0.2923	0.3605	0.8072	0.6849
BASE	0.2639	0.2790	0.7039	0.8939

Table 6.18: CV of HHI_{norm} for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

HHI_{norm} increased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, suggesting a decreasing DoD with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

Finally, HHI_{norm} decreased with an increasingly equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes. This is plausible, because an equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes means that validating nodes have the same chance to propose the next valid block, and thus receiving the block reward, leading to an equal distribution of tokens among validating nodes, and thus a low HHI_{norm} .

Figure 6.10: HHI_{norm} for different $n_{security_confirmation}$.

$n_{security_confirmation}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.3004	0.3015	0.9467	0.6110
6	0.2639	0.2790	0.7039	0.8939
10	0.4737	0.3074	0.8336	0.7523

Table 6.19: CV of HHI_{norm} when varying $n_{security_confirmation}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.11: HHI_{norm} for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Tables 6.16 to 6.20, show that the CV for HHI_{norm} did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for HHI_{norm} are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.3393	0.3050	0.4913	0.5901
D4	0.2990	0.3169	0.4850	0.5126
D3	0.2970	0.3103	0.9209	0.5614
D2/Base	0.2639	0.2790	0.7039	0.8939
D1	0.3751	0.4009	0.4572	0.5232

Table 6.20: CV of HHI_{norm} for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Gini Coefficient $Gini$

The Gini Coefficient $Gini$ represents the degree of inequality in terms of token ownership among validating nodes [5]. Therefore, one can argue analogous to HHI_{norm} , which is also based on token ownership.

A low $Gini$ suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good DoD [5].

$Gini$ decreased with an increasing \bar{I}_B , which is plausible and can be explained analogous as for HHI_{norm} . Furthermore, one can see that the impact of the \bar{I}_B on $Gini$ is even more prominent for the RING topology. For $\bar{I}_B \leq 60$ ms the $Gini$ is higher for the RING topology, but as of $\bar{I}_B \geq 150$ ms the $Gini$ for the RING topology is below the $Gini$ for the NET topology, and the $Gini$ for the RING topology decreases faster with an increasing \bar{I}_B than for the NET topology.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, Gini)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, Gini)$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong negative correlation between \bar{I}_B and $Gini$. The corresponding p -values, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, Gini)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, Gini)$ are statistically significant. However, $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, Gini) \approx 0.0457$ was borderline significant.

Figure 6.12: $Gini$ for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.0967	0.0901	0.1780	0.1741
60	0.0944	0.1000	0.1639	0.1563
150	0.1007	0.1000	0.1715	0.1721
600	0.0996	0.1049	0.1903	0.1913

Table 6.21: CV of *Gini* when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Gini increased with an increasing B_{\max} , which is plausible with an argumentation analogous to HHI_{norm} . For all maximum block sizes, the *Gini* was higher for the NET topology than the RING topology, but the *Gini* increases faster with an increasing B_{\max} for the RING topology, until the *Gini* for both topologies meet at $B_{\max} = 8$ MB. This suggests that the NET topology can handle larger blocks better than the RING topology.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, Gini)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, Gini)$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate a positive correlation between B_{\max} and *Gini*. The corresponding *p*-values are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, Gini)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, Gini)$ are statistically significant.

Figure 6.13: *Gini* for different B_{\max} .

For the NET topology, the *Gini* was not affected much by different throughput configurations. However, for the RING topology, the *Gini* decreased with an increasingly faster throughput configuration, with a big decrease from the configuration C to the configuration S, which is plausible and can be explained with observation 3.

The *Gini* increased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, suggesting a decreasing DoD with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

Finally, one can see that *Gini* decreases with an increasingly equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, which is plausible, and can be explained analogous to the discussion for HHI_{norm} .

B_{\max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.1015	0.1000	0.1578	0.1626
250 kB	0.0971	0.1032	0.1703	0.1709
500 kB	0.0990	0.1003	0.1731	0.1791
1 MB	0.0996	0.1049	0.1903	0.1913
2 MB	0.1039	0.1027	0.2052	0.2054
4 MB	0.1014	0.0957	0.1921	0.1816
8 MB	0.1020	0.0988	0.1648	0.1648

Table 6.22: CV of *Gini* when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.14: *Gini* for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.1102	0.1028	0.2359	0.2632
S	0.1031	0.1087	0.1877	0.1963
BASE	0.0996	0.1049	0.1903	0.1913

Table 6.23: CV of *Gini* for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.1108	0.1132	0.2023	0.2036
6	0.0996	0.1049	0.1903	0.1913
10	0.1002	0.0987	0.1801	0.1923

Table 6.24: CV of *Gini* when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Tables 6.21 to 6.25, show that the CV for *Gini* did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for *Gini* are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Figure 6.15: *Gini* for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

Figure 6.16: *Gini* for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.0909	0.0928	0.1526	0.1638
D4	0.0936	0.0929	0.1553	0.1639
D3	0.1077	0.1011	0.1882	0.1947
D2/Base	0.0996	0.1049	0.1903	0.1913
D1	0.1160	0.1094	0.1967	0.1917

Table 6.25: CV of *Gini* for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Availability (Scalability) A_{Sca}

A high availability regarding scalability A_{Sca} suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good scalability [5].

For both topologies, the A_{Sca} increased with an increasing \bar{I}_B , which is plausible, because the A_{Sca} strongly depends on the time for synchronization of validating nodes [5], and a longer \bar{I}_B means that validating nodes have more time to synchronize, before the next block is proposed. For the NET topology, the A_{Sca} reached a plateau at $\bar{I}_B \geq 150$ s.

As specified in table 6.8, $\rho_{RING,1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{Sca})$, indicates a strong positive correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average A_{Sca} for the RING topology, and the corresponding p -value indicates that $\rho_{RING,1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{Sca})$ is statistically significant. For the NET topology $\rho_{NET,1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{Sca})$ indicates a weak positive correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average A_{Sca} , but the corresponding p -value does not suggest statistical significance of $\rho_{NET,1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{Sca})$.

Figure 6.17: A_{Sca} for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.2722	0.2646	0.6774	0.7031
60	0.2339	0.2543	0.6518	0.6132
150	0.2297	0.2354	0.6331	0.6158
600	0.1278	0.1301	0.1664	0.1753

Table 6.26: CV of A_{Sca} when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, the A_{Sca} increased with an increasing B_{max} up to $B_{max} = 2$ MB. For $B_{max} > 2$ MB the A_{Sca} slightly decreased for the NET topology, and drastically decreased for the RING topology, which suggests that the NET topology can handle larger blocks better. Observation 1 shows that it takes longer for a block to propagate through the P2P network in the RING topology than in the NET topology, and this effect is even more prominent for larger blocks, because larger blocks take longer to propagate. Therefore, it is plausible that the NET topology can handle larger blocks better. The drastic decrease in A_{Sca} for $B_{max} > 2$ MB in the RING topology, could be caused by blocks being so large, that they do not always reach all validating nodes before the next block is proposed.

As specified in table 6.9, $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sca}})$ indicates a weak positive correlation between B_{max} and the average A_{Sca} , but the corresponding p -value does not suggest that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sca}})$ is statistically significant. The $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sca}})$ suggests that there does not exist a correlation between B_{max} and the average A_{Sca} for the RING topology.

Figure 6.18: A_{Sca} for different B_{max} .

B_{max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.1545	0.1559	0.1513	0.1581
250 kB	0.1537	0.1521	0.1470	0.1425
500 kB	0.1421	0.1421	0.1459	0.1504
1 MB	0.1278	0.1301	0.1664	0.1753
2 MB	0.2006	0.1876	0.3533	0.3419
4 MB	0.2438	0.2405	0.6078	0.6221
8 MB	0.2302	0.2362	0.6433	0.6219

Table 6.27: CV of A_{Sca} when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

The A_{Sca} was not affected much by different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.1626	0.1426	0.2040	0.2136
D4	0.1484	0.1511	0.1921	0.2096
D3	0.1372	0.1345	0.1730	0.1646
D2/Base	0.1278	0.1301	0.1664	0.1753
D1	0.1376	0.1302	0.1590	0.1562

Table 6.28: CV of A_{Sca} for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.19: A_{Sca} for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

For the RING topology the A_{Sca} increased with an increasingly better throughput configuration, which is plausible, because the A_{Sca} strongly depends on the throughput [5]. For the NET topology, the A_{Sca} decreases slightly from throughput configuration C to S then increasing to the BASE configuration and reaching a high point. This suggests, that the NET topology has a higher availability, in a network with a higher expected throughput and lower expected latency, where some links between validating nodes might fail, than in a network where links do not fail, but the expected throughput is lower and the expected latency is higher. This is plausible and can be explained with the following observation:

Observation 4 *In the NET topology, nodes are arranged in a subgraph with connectivity 4, i.e. if a link fails, the validating node still has 3 other links over which it can propagate messages and participate in the P2P network. The chance of all 4 links failing at the same time, cutting off the validating node from the network is low. It is thus even less likely, that multiple validating nodes are cut off from the network at the same time, forming their own independent partition. However, if all links are slow, there is no alternative faster path for messages to be propagated along.*

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.1570	0.1466	0.8931	0.9025
S	0.1401	0.1400	0.1955	0.1975
BASE	0.1278	0.1301	0.1664	0.1753

Table 6.29: CV of A_{Sca} for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Finally, for both topologies the A_{Sca} decreased with an increasing $n_{security_confirmation}$, which is plausible, because with a higher $n_{security_confirmation}$ it takes longer for a transaction to be considered confirmed, and the number of confirmed transactions per time slice is thus lower.

Figure 6.20: A_{Sca} for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Figure 6.21: A_{Sca} for different $n_{security_confirmation}$.

$n_{security_confirmation}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.1338	0.1342	0.1700	0.1810
6	0.1278	0.1301	0.1664	0.1753
10	0.1413	0.1408	0.1706	0.1845

Table 6.30: CV of A_{Sca} when varying $n_{security_confirmation}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Tables 6.26 to 6.30, show that the CV for A_{Sca} did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for A_{Sca} are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Transaction Throughput TPS

A high transaction throughput TPS suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good scalability [5].

In all experiments and for all configurations, the TPS was higher for the NET topology than the RING topology, which is plausible, because transactions and blocks take longer to be propagated through the P2P network in the RING topology, than in the NET topology, as discussed in observation 1.

For the RING topology, TPS increased with an increasing \bar{I}_B . For the NET topology TPS increased for $\bar{I}_B \leq 150$ s, and remained stable for $150 \text{ s} \leq \bar{I}_B \leq 600$ s.

As specified in table 6.8, $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, TPS)$ indicates a weak positive correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average TPS for the NET topology. However $p_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, TPS)$ is very high, indicating that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, TPS)$ is not statistically significant. Furthermore, as specified in table 6.8, $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, TPS)$ indicates a strong correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average TPS for the RING topology, and the corresponding p -value suggests that $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, TPS)$ is statistically significant.

In the experiment a new transaction is submitted to the network on average every $\bar{I}_{\text{trx}} = 100$ ms, therefore on average $N_{\text{trx}} = \frac{\bar{I}_B}{\bar{I}_{\text{trx}}}$ transactions are submitted to the network every \bar{I}_B . With an increasing \bar{I}_B N_{trx} also increases. Let \bar{S}_{trx} be the average size of a transaction, then in each block on average $\bar{B}_{\text{free}} = B_{\text{max}} - N_{\text{trx}} * \bar{S}_{\text{trx}}$ space is unused. One can see that the unused space decreases with an increasing \bar{I}_B , leading to a better TPS . However, according to existing literature, TPS should decrease with longer \bar{I}_B , because it takes more time until enough succeeding blocks are appended for a transaction to be considered confirmed [2]. Once the \bar{B}_{free} approaches 0, the effect of the time it takes to confirm blocks, causes TPS to decrease again, with longer \bar{I}_B . Therefore the results for TPS in the experiments where \bar{I}_B was varied, can be explained but are not obviously plausible, and need further investigation.

Figure 6.22: TPS for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.2722	0.2646	0.6778	0.7031
60	0.2337	0.2542	0.6520	0.6131
150	0.2296	0.2355	0.6330	0.6157
600	0.1279	0.1301	0.1665	0.1753

Table 6.31: CV of TPS when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, the TPS increased with an increasing B_{\max} up to $B_{\max} = 2$ MB, then slightly decreasing for larger blocks for the NET topology, and drastically decreasing for larger blocks for the RING topology. This is plausible, because with a larger B_{\max} , more transactions can be added to a single block [2], i.e. more transactions can be included in the blockchain per \bar{I}_B , thus increasing TPS. However, with an increasing B_{\max} the time for the block to reach a majority of validating nodes also increases, which is a bottleneck, especially in the RING topology. The experiment results for TPS also suggest that the NET topology can handle larger blocks better than the RING topology, which is plausible and can be explained analogous to the argument presented for A_{Sca} .

As specified in table 6.8, $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, \text{TPS})$ indicates a weak positive correlation between B_{\max} and the average TPS for the NET topology, and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$ indicates that there does not exist a correlation between the B_{\max} and the average TPS for the RING topology. However, both corresponding p -values are above the threshold of 0.05 and thus suggest that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, H)$ are not statistically significant.

Figure 6.23: TPS for different B_{\max} .

For the RING topology (at 1000 rounds), the TPS is as low as $\text{TPS} \approx 20 \frac{\text{transaction}}{\text{s}}$ for throughput configuration C, but rapidly increases to reach $\text{TPS} \approx 81 \frac{\text{transaction}}{\text{s}}$ for the BASE configuration. For the NET topology, TPS decreases from configuration C to S, then increasing again to configuration B. This shows again, that the NET can handle some failed links better than an overall slower network, which is plausible and can be explained with observation 4. For

B_{\max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.1546	0.1559	0.1514	0.1580
250 kB	0.1537	0.1521	0.1468	0.1424
500 kB	0.1423	0.1422	0.1459	0.1505
1 MB	0.1279	0.1301	0.1665	0.1753
2 MB	0.2006	0.1876	0.3534	0.3419
4 MB	0.2437	0.2405	0.6079	0.6221
8 MB	0.2301	0.2362	0.6432	0.6219

Table 6.32: CV of TPS when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

the NET topology TPS never falls below $68 \frac{\text{transaction}}{\text{s}}$, which shows that the NET topology can handle slow and failed links better than the RING topology, which is plausible.

Figure 6.24: TPS for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.1570	0.1466	0.8931	0.9024
S	0.1402	0.1400	0.1955	0.1975
BASE	0.1279	0.1301	0.1665	0.1753

Table 6.33: CV of TPS for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For the RING topology, the TPS increased with an increasingly equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes. For the NET topology, the TPS increased up to the BASE configuration, but decreased again from the BASE configuration to configuration D1. Since the TPS metric only focuses on transactions included in the mainchain and neglects overhead to process transactions not included in the mainchain, the TPS may underestimate the actual maximum throughput of the blockchain system under investigation [5], which may explain the decrease of TPS for the NET topology in configuration D1.

Figure 6.25: TPS for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.1626	0.1427	0.2040	0.2136
D4	0.1484	0.1511	0.1920	0.2096
D3	0.1371	0.1347	0.1731	0.1645
D2/Base	0.1279	0.1301	0.1665	0.1753
D1	0.1376	0.1302	0.1591	0.1562

Table 6.34: CV of TPS for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, the TPS decreased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, which is plausible, because a higher $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ means that it takes longer for a transaction to be considered confirmed, and thus less transactions can be confirmed in the same time slice, leading to a lower TPS.

Figure 6.26: TPS for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.1338	0.1342	0.1700	0.1811
6	0.1279	0.1301	0.1665	0.1753
10	0.1412	0.1408	0.1706	0.1845

Table 6.35: CV of TPS when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Tables 6.31 to 6.35, show that the CV for TPS did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for TPS are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Availability (Security) A_{Sec}

A high availability regarding security A_{Sec} suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good security [5].

The A_{Sec} increased with an increasing \bar{I}_B for both topologies. A_{Sec} was consistently higher for the NET topology than the RING topology, which is plausible, because with observation 3, one can see that even a single failed link slows down the simulated blockchain system significantly, leading to a failure, and thus one can expect more failures to occur in the RING topology.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{\text{Sec}})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{\text{Sec}})$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average A_{Sec} . However, the corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.8, are for both topologies above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{\text{Sec}})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, A_{\text{Sec}})$ are not statistically significant.

Figure 6.27: A_{Sec} for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.0347	0.0350	0.0307	0.0299
60	0.0304	0.0303	0.0285	0.0296
150	0.0283	0.0279	0.0262	0.0277
600	0.0223	0.0236	0.0215	0.0228

Table 6.36: CV of A_{Sec} when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies the A_{Sec} was lowest for $B_{\text{max}} = 75$ kB, and sharply increased to $B_{\text{max}} = 250$ kB, whereas the effect was even more drastic for the RING topology. This is plausible, because the smaller a block, the less transactions can be included, the less transactions can be confirmed per \bar{I}_B (here 10 min), meaning that the TPS already is close to the failure threshold $f_{\text{threshold}}$, making what is assumed a failure in the experiment incredibly likely. The inherent limitation of A_{Sec} is, that it is unclear what type of failure should be considered to estimate it [5], which in this case makes the results for A_{Sec} less meaningful.

For $B_{\text{max}} \geq 250$ kB, the A_{Sec} decreased for both topologies. This is plausible, because A_{Sec} decreases (low availability), if validating nodes synchronize slowly [5], and larger blocks take longer to propagate through the P2P network, thus taking longer to be accepted by the majority of validating nodes.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sec}})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sec}})$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate that there does not exist a correlation between B_{max} and the average A_{Sec} . However, the corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.9, are for both topologies above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sec}})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, A_{\text{Sec}})$ are not statistically significant.

Figure 6.28: A_{Sec} for different B_{max} .

For both topologies, the A_{Sec} was not significantly influenced by the distribution of hashing power among validating nodes.

B_{\max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.0287	0.0256	0.0264	0.0272
250 kB	0.0269	0.0253	0.0241	0.0251
500 kB	0.0239	0.0244	0.0229	0.0231
1 MB	0.0223	0.0236	0.0215	0.0228
2 MB	0.0238	0.0242	0.0233	0.0217
4 MB	0.0281	0.0276	0.0245	0.0264
8 MB	0.0296	0.0257	0.0292	0.0280

Table 6.37: CV of A_{Sec} when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.29: A_{Sec} for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.0253	0.0255	0.0248	0.0253
D4	0.0239	0.0258	0.0240	0.0246
D3	0.0208	0.0227	0.0219	0.0228
D2/Base	0.0223	0.0236	0.0215	0.0228
D1	0.0216	0.0237	0.0232	0.0206

Table 6.38: CV of A_{Sec} for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, the A_{Sec} decreased from throughput configuration C to configuration S, then increasing again for the BASE configuration. The A_{Sec} is influenced by how quickly the validating nodes in the P2P network reach consensus, and all links in configuration S have a lower throughput and higher latency than in the BASE, thus the overall throughput and latency of the P2P network are worse in configuration S, leading to a worse A_{Sec} .

Observation 5 While in configuration C, links can fail completely with a probability of 10%, the expected throughput and expected latency for all links is approximately equal to the expected throughput and expected latency of links in the BASE configuration.

Due to observation 5, it is plausible, that the A_{Sec} was lower for configuration S than for configuration C or the BASE configuration. One can see that the possibility of some links failing completely has less of an effect on A_{Sec} than an overall slower network configuration.

Figure 6.30: A_{Sca} for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.0265	0.0253	0.0258	0.0277
S	0.0244	0.0231	0.0223	0.0226
BASE	0.0223	0.0236	0.0215	0.0228

Table 6.39: CV of A_{Sec} for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Finally, the A_{Sec} decreased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, which is plausible, because with a higher $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, it takes longer for a transaction to be considered confirmed, thus less transactions can be confirmed per time slice, and the transaction throughput is thus moved closer to the $f_{\text{threshold}}$. However, this result is not meaningful, because it is inherently dependent on the specified $f_{\text{threshold}}$ and what 3SIM considers a failure, which is an inherent problem of calculating A_{Sec} [5], as discussed above.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.0209	0.0211	0.0185	0.0191
6	0.0223	0.0236	0.0215	0.0228
10	0.0264	0.0263	0.0248	0.0267

Table 6.40: CV of A_{Sec} when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Tables 6.36 to 6.40, show that the CV for A_{Sec} was below the threshold of 0.05 for all simulation runs of all experiments, suggesting that the simulation results for A_{Sec} did converge.

Figure 6.31: A_{Sca} for different $n_{security_confirmation}$.

Consistency *Cons*

Consistency *Cons* is the average confirmation latency for all confirmed blocks [5]. A low *Cons* is desirable, as it indicates that transactions are processed quickly, which facilitates validating nodes to offer a consistent view of the ledger and mitigates Byzantine behavior [5].

Cons increased with an increasing \bar{I}_B for both topologies, which is plausible, because the *CL* is expected to increase with an increasing \bar{I}_B [2]. On average a block is expected to be confirmed every $n_{security_confirmation} * \bar{I}_B$, meaning that a higher $n_{security_confirmation}$ or a higher \bar{I}_B lead to a higher block confirmation time, while the block proposal time is on average expected to be \bar{I}_B . Therefore, for $n_{security_confirmation} > 1$, the expected difference between block confirmation time and block proposal time increases with an increasing \bar{I}_B , and ergo it is plausible that *Cons* increases for an increasing \bar{I}_B (for $n_{security_confirmation} = 6$, as set in the BASE configuration). Furthermore, it is thus plausible that *Cons* increases with an increasing $n_{security_confirmation}$, which can be seen in the experiment where $n_{security_confirmation}$ was varied, for both topologies.

$\rho_{NET,1000}(\bar{I}_B, Cons)$ and $\rho_{RING,1000}(\bar{I}_B, Cons)$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong positive correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average *Cons*. The corresponding *p*-values, as specified in table 6.8, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{NET,1000}(\bar{I}_B, Cons)$ and $\rho_{RING,1000}(\bar{I}_B, Cons)$ are statistically significant.

For both topologies, the *Cons* increased with an increasing B_{max} , which is plausible, because larger blocks take longer to propagate through the P2P network, and to reach a majority of validating nodes. The *Cons* increased more dramatically for the RING topology than the NET topology, which is plausible and can be explained with observation 1.

$\rho_{NET,1000}(B_{max}, Cons)$ and $\rho_{RING,1000}(B_{max}, Cons)$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate a positive correlation between B_{max} and the average *Cons*. The corresponding *p*-values, as

Figure 6.32: *Cons* for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.2121	0.2249	0.3267	0.3614
60	0.2627	0.2583	0.3706	0.3349
150	0.2506	0.2520	0.3319	0.3520
600	0.1534	0.1755	0.2286	0.2357

Table 6.41: *CV* of *Cons* when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.33: *Cons* for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

specified in table 6.9, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, \text{Cons})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, \text{Cons})$ are statistically significant.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.2360	0.2079	0.3599	0.4825
6	0.1534	0.1755	0.2286	0.2357
10	0.1846	0.1820	0.1715	0.2350

Table 6.42: CV of *Cons* when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.34: *Cons* for different B_{max} .

B_{max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.2055	0.1703	0.1590	0.1697
250 kB	0.2160	0.1599	0.1546	0.2095
500 kB	0.1523	0.1581	0.1770	0.1686
1 MB	0.1534	0.1755	0.2286	0.2357
2 MB	0.2374	0.2286	0.3137	0.2993
4 MB	0.3375	0.2909	0.3703	0.3509
8 MB	0.2576	0.2892	0.3329	0.3471

Table 6.43: CV of *Cons* when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Cons remained relatively stable for both topologies, with different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

For the NET topology *Cons* was relatively stable for different throughput configurations. For the RING topology, *Cons* was very high for configuration C ($Cons > 340$ min for the experiment with 1000 rounds), and decreased for configuration S and further for the BASE configuration. This is plausible, because the RING topology cannot handle links failing completely well, as outlined in observation 3.

Figure 6.35: *Cons* for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.2216	0.1850	0.2825	0.3023
D4	0.2100	0.2076	0.2253	0.3059
D3	0.1633	0.1817	0.2215	0.2175
D2/Base	0.1534	0.1755	0.2286	0.2357
D1	0.1724	0.1679	0.2084	0.2340

Table 6.44: *CV* of *Cons* for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.36: *Cons* for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Tables 6.41 to 6.45, show that the *CV* for *Cons* did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for *Cons* are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.2743	0.2292	0.5677	0.5427
S	0.1872	0.1708	0.2369	0.2379
BASE	0.1534	0.1755	0.2286	0.2357

Table 6.45: CV of Cons for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Fault Tolerance FT

The fault tolerance FT encompasses the throughput delta ΔTPS and the confirmation latency delta ΔCL , which will be discussed individually in the following.

A low ΔTPS and low ΔCL , suggest that the TPS and CL of the blockchain system do not change dramatically if the blockchain system fails, thus making it more fault tolerant, and therefore more secure [5].

For both topologies, the ΔTPS increased with an increasing \bar{I}_B up to $\bar{I}_B = 150$ s, and then decreased again for $\bar{I}_B = 10$ min. The RING topology had a higher ΔTPS than the NET topology for $20 \text{ s} \leq \bar{I}_B \leq 60 \text{ s}$. The ΔTPS increased more dramatically for the NET topology than the RING topology for $\bar{I}_B \leq 150 \text{ s}$, and for $\bar{I}_B \geq 150 \text{ s}$ the ΔTPS decreased strongly for the RING topology, and only slightly decreased for the NET topology.

Table 6.8 shows that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, FT_{\Delta TPS})$ indicates a positive correlation and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, FT_{\Delta TPS})$ indicates a negative correlation between \bar{I}_B and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, but the corresponding p -values are above the threshold of 0.05, therefore the experiment results do not indicate a statistically significant correlation between \bar{I}_B and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$.

The ΔCL increased with an increasing \bar{I}_B for both topologies.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, FT_{\Delta CL})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, FT_{\Delta CL})$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong positive correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average $FT_{\Delta CL}$. The corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.8, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, FT_{\Delta CL})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, FT_{\Delta CL})$ are statistically significant.

B_{\max}	$FT_{\Delta CL}$				$FT_{\Delta TPS}$			
	NET		RING		NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.7812	0.7633	0.7255	0.7134	0.1438	0.1411	0.1615	0.2440
60	0.7135	0.6837	0.6416	0.6418	0.1486	0.1514	0.1507	0.1758
150	0.6687	0.6642	0.5862	0.5822	0.1574	0.1593	0.1604	0.8501
600	0.7049	0.7229	0.7770	0.7095	0.1364	0.1533	0.3632	0.2604

Table 6.46: CV of FT when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For the NET topology, the ΔTPS remained relatively stable with varying B_{\max} . For the RING topology, the ΔTPS increased with an increasing B_{\max} , flattening out for $B_{\max} \geq 4 \text{ MB}$.

Figure 6.37: FT for different \bar{I}_B .

Table 6.8 shows that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, FT_{\Delta TPS})$ indicates a very weak positive correlation between B_{\max} and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ for the NET topology, but the corresponding p -value is above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is not statistically significant. Table 6.8 also shows for the RING topology, that $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, FT_{\Delta TPS})$ indicates a positive correlation between B_{\max} and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, with the corresponding $p \approx 0.0567$ suggesting that the correlation is borderline significant.

For both topologies, the ΔCL increased with an increasing B_{\max} up to $B_{\max} = 4$ MB then slightly decreasing again for $B_{\max} = 8$ MB.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, FT_{\Delta CL})$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, FT_{\Delta CL})$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate a positive correlation between B_{\max} and the average $FT_{\Delta CL}$. As specified in table 6.9, for the NET topology the corresponding $p \approx 0.0650$ suggests that the correlation is borderline significant, while for the RING topology the corresponding p -value is below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant.

The ΔTPS remained relatively stable for both topologies with different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes. For the NET topology the ΔCL increased from configuration D5 to configuration D3, then sharply decreased for the BASE configuration and increased again for configuration D1. For the RING topology, the ΔCL moved inversely to the ΔCL for the NET topology, for configurations D4, D3, the BASE configuration and configuration D1.

In the experiment where different throughput configurations were tested, for the NET topology, the ΔTPS decreased from configuration C to configuration S, and then increased again for the BASE configuration, which is plausible and can be explained with observation 4.

Figure 6.38: FT for different B_{\max} .

B_{\max}	$FT_{\Delta CL}$				$FT_{\Delta TPS}$			
	NET		RING		NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	0.9957	0.9729	0.8684	0.9339	0.2083	0.2061	0.2482	0.2924
250 kB	0.7879	0.7715	0.7566	0.7698	0.1963	0.1986	0.2168	0.2119
500 kB	0.7618	0.7272	0.7720	0.7286	0.1949	0.2011	0.2442	0.2585
1 MB	0.7049	0.7229	0.7770	0.7095	0.1364	0.1533	0.3632	0.2604
2 MB	0.6482	0.6494	0.6368	0.6261	0.1688	0.1805	0.1781	0.4151
4 MB	0.6999	0.6573	0.5781	0.6075	0.1654	0.1869	0.1634	0.1692
8 MB	0.7315	0.6659	0.6212	0.6251	0.1782	0.4388	0.1614	0.1608

Table 6.47: CV of FT when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

B_{\max}	$FT_{\Delta CL}$				$FT_{\Delta TPS}$			
	NET		RING		NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.7399	0.7659	0.7604	0.7611	0.1910	0.2043	0.2582	0.2469
D4	0.7273	0.7297	0.7626	0.7702	0.2150	0.1995	0.2222	0.2252
D3	0.6826	0.7016	0.7736	0.7239	0.9502	0.1844	0.2023	0.2108
D2/Base	0.7049	0.7229	0.7770	0.7095	0.1364	0.1533	0.3632	0.2604
D1	0.6745	0.6905	0.7641	0.7508	0.4251	0.1894	0.1915	0.2371

Table 6.48: CV of FT for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.39: FT for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

For the RING topology, the ΔTPS increased slightly from configuration C to configuration S, and then increased sharply for the BASE configuration.

For the NET topology, the ΔCL remained relatively stable, but slightly increased for configuration S, which is plausible and can be explained with observation 4. For the RING topology ΔCL was high for configuration C, which is plausible because with observation 3, one can see that if two or more links fail, consensus can only be reached once the independent partitions are resolved, and in the mean-time, no blocks can be confirmed, thus leading to a low CL during failures, and in turn leading to a high ΔCL . From configuration S to the BASE configuration the ΔCL decreased slightly for the RING topology.

B_{\max}	$FT_{\Delta CL}$				$FT_{\Delta TPS}$			
	NET		RING		NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.7754	0.7594	0.6381	0.6430	0.1956	0.2103	0.4399	0.7086
S	0.6640	0.6722	0.7343	0.7343	0.1573	0.2523	0.2205	0.2162
BASE	0.7049	0.7229	0.7770	0.7095	0.1364	0.1533	0.3632	0.2604

Table 6.49: CV of FT for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, the ΔTPS decreased from $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 2$ to $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 6$, and then increased again for $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 10$.

For both topologies, the ΔCL increased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$, which is plausible because the CL during normal operation increases with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

Figure 6.40: FT for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Figure 6.41: FT for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

Tables 6.46 to 6.50, show that the CV for $FT_{\Delta CL}$ and for $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for FT are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

B_{\max}	$FT_{\Delta CL}$				$FT_{\Delta TPS}$			
	NET		RING		NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.5782	0.6138	0.7099	0.6938	0.1437	0.1385	0.1496	0.2272
6	0.7049	0.7229	0.7770	0.7095	0.1364	0.1533	0.3632	0.2604
10	0.7526	0.7359	0.7370	0.8019	0.2622	0.2409	0.2466	0.5878

Table 6.50: CV of FT when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Reliability $R(t)$

$R(t)$ denotes the probability that a blockchain system operates unreliably within the timespan t , thus a lower $R(t)$ is desirable. A low $R(t)$ suggests that the simulated blockchain system is reliable and therefore more secure [5].

Similarly to FT , it is unclear when a blockchain system should be considered failed for the calculation of $R(t)$ [5].

To assess the reliability $R(t)$ of the simulated blockchain systems an observation timespan of $t = 24$ h was chosen. Hereinafter let $R = R(24 \text{ h})$.

For both topologies, the $R < 0.0001$ for $\bar{I}_B \leq 150$ s, and then sharply increased for $\bar{I}_B = 10$ min.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, R)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, R)$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong positive correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average R . The corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.8, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, R)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, R)$ are statistically significant.

Figure 6.42: R for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	14.7478	27.3783	22.3093	31.6021
60	8.2574	8.6195	17.2767	19.4672
150	4.3856	3.9813	4.4267	4.8920
600	1.2193	1.3002	1.2302	1.3152

Table 6.51: CV of R when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

In the experiment where B_{\max} was varied, R increased for the RING topology for $B_{\max} \leq 2$ MB, and then decreased again sharply for $B_{\max} > 2$ MB. For the NET topology, the R increased for $B_{\max} \leq 1$ MB, then slightly decreased again to $B_{\max} = 4$ MB and remained relatively stable thereafter.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, R)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, R)$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate that there does not exist a correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average R . Furthermore, the corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.9, are for both topologies above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\max}, R)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\max}, R)$ are not statistically significant.

Figure 6.43: R for different B_{\max} .

For both topologies, R was not influenced significantly by different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

For the NET topology, R increased from throughput configuration C to configuration S, and decreased for the BASE configuration, which is plausible and can be explained with observation 5. For the RING topology, the R was high for throughput configuration C, decreased for configuration S and for the BASE configuration R remained stable (in the experiment with 1000 rounds) or increased (in the experiment with 500 rounds). This is plausible, because the RING topology is affected severely by failing links, as discussed in observation 3.

B_{\max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	22.3383	0.0000	22.3383	31.6070
250 kB	1.2490	1.3498	0.9697	0.9626
500 kB	1.1468	1.1102	0.9964	0.9976
1 MB	1.2193	1.3002	1.2302	1.3152
2 MB	1.8192	1.9036	1.6979	1.6956
4 MB	2.3980	2.2499	3.0097	2.8877
8 MB	2.5441	2.3149	4.0270	3.8927

Table 6.52: CV of R when varying B_{\max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.44: R for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	1.7485	1.6622	1.3277	1.4610
D4	1.6891	1.8197	1.3114	1.3775
D3	1.3696	1.3262	1.2552	1.2641
D2/Base	1.2193	1.3002	1.2302	1.3152
D1	1.3713	1.2718	1.2816	1.2240

Table 6.53: CV of R for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	1.3010	1.2835	1.9876	1.9353
S	1.4291	1.3716	2.0164	1.8122
BASE	1.2193	1.3002	1.2302	1.3152

Table 6.54: CV of R for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.45: R for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Figure 6.46: R for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.8611	0.7893	0.8566	0.7881
6	1.2193	1.3002	1.2302	1.3152
10	1.9199	1.9342	1.5385	1.6036

Table 6.55: CV of R when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, R decreased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

Tables 6.51 to 6.55, show that the CV for R did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment and was extremely high. This suggests that the simulation results for R are very highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Stale Block Rate SBR

If multiple validating nodes propose a new block simultaneously, only the fastest-propagating block is accepted, while the other blocks become stale [5]. Therefore, a low stale block rate SBR suggests that the simulated blockchain system has a good security [5].

For both topologies, the SBR decreased with an increasing \bar{I}_B , which is plausible, because a shorter \bar{I}_B means that validating nodes might not be aware of newly created blocks fast enough, which leads to temporary forks and thus an increased SBR [2].

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, SBR)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, SBR)$, as specified in table 6.8, both indicate a strong negative correlation between \bar{I}_B and the average SBR . The corresponding p -values, as specified in table 6.8, are for both topologies above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(\bar{I}_B, SBR)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(\bar{I}_B, SBR)$ are not statistically significant.

Figure 6.47: SBR for different \bar{I}_B .

\bar{I}_B [s]	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
20	0.7278	0.3527	1.1741	1.0728
60	0.4470	0.6044	0.8324	0.8365
150	0.4768	0.6936	0.7326	0.8905
600	0.4606	0.4275	1.0627	1.1887

Table 6.56: CV of SBR when varying \bar{I}_B for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For both topologies, SBR increased with an increasing B_{max} , increasing faster for the RING topology. This is plausible, because larger blocks take longer to propagate through the P2P network, thus making stale blocks more likely, and this effect is more severe for the RING topology, as discussed in observation 1.

$\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, SBR)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, SBR)$, as specified in table 6.9, both indicate a positive correlation between B_{max} and the average SBR . The corresponding p -values, as

specified in table 6.9, are for both topologies below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that $\rho_{\text{NET},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, SBR)$ and $\rho_{\text{RING},1000}(B_{\text{max}}, SBR)$ are statistically significant.

Figure 6.48: SBR for different B_{max} .

B_{max}	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
75 kB	1.1039	0.6947	0.6613	0.6688
250 kB	0.6526	0.5197	0.4581	0.5550
500 kB	0.4195	0.6336	1.1860	0.5336
1 MB	0.4606	0.4275	1.0627	1.1887
2 MB	0.4968	0.6087	1.0432	0.7701
4 MB	0.6519	0.5479	1.3582	0.9042
8 MB	0.5934	0.6471	0.8591	0.8253

Table 6.57: CV of SBR when varying B_{max} for 500 and 1000 rounds.

For the RING topology the SBR decreased with an increasingly equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, while for the NET topology, the SBR remained relatively stable for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes, with an outlier for the BASE configuration.

The more likely network partitions are to occur, the higher the SBR [5]. For the NET topology, the SBR remained relatively stable for different throughput configurations, only slightly increasing for configuration S, which is plausible, because network partitions are unlikely in the NET topology, as discussed in observation 4. For the RING topology, the SBR was especially high for configuration C and then decreased fast to configuration S, and slightly decreased to the BASE configuration, which is plausible because partitions are very likely in a ring with failing links, as discussed in observation 3.

For the RING topology, the SBR increased with an increasing $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$. For the NET topology SBR decreased from $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 2$ to $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 6$ and then increased again for $n_{\text{security_confirmation}} = 10$.

Figure 6.49: SBR for different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
D5	0.5180	0.4899	0.8569	1.7908
D4	0.6604	0.5426	0.9093	0.8367
D3	0.3917	0.4888	1.1597	0.7453
D2/Base	0.4606	0.4275	1.0627	1.1887
D1	0.4927	0.4642	0.5301	0.8960

Table 6.58: CV of SBR for configurations with different distribution of hashing power among validating nodes, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.50: SBR for configurations with different throughput and latency.

Tables 6.56 to 6.60, show that the CV for SBR did not fall below the threshold of 0.05 for any simulation run of any experiment, suggesting that the simulation results for SBR are highly dispersed and more simulation rounds are needed to get converging results.

Configuration	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
C	0.5882	0.5762	1.1827	1.3849
S	0.3276	0.4513	0.8928	0.7493
BASE	0.4606	0.4275	1.0627	1.1887

Table 6.59: CV of SBR for configurations with different throughput and latency, for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Figure 6.51: SBR for different $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$.

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$	NET		RING	
	500r	1000r	500r	1000r
2	0.4808	0.5443	1.1020	0.9422
6	0.4606	0.4275	1.0627	1.1887
10	0.8559	0.4223	0.7761	1.1707

Table 6.60: CV of SBR when varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for 500 and 1000 rounds.

Pairwise Partial Correlations

A matrix with the columns

$$\{\text{topology}, \bar{I}_B, B_{\max}, A_{\text{Sca}}, A_{\text{Sec}}, \text{Cons}, FT_{\Delta CL}, FT_{\Delta TPS}, \text{Gini}, HHI_{\text{norm}}, R, H, \text{SBR}, \text{TPS}\}$$

was filled with results from the experiments $\text{ex}_{\bar{I}_B, \text{NET}, 1000}^-$, $\text{ex}_{\bar{I}_B, \text{NET}, 1000}^+$, $\text{ex}_{B_{\max}, \text{NET}, 1000}$, $\text{ex}_{B_{\max}, \text{RING}, 1000}$, and the pairwise partial pearson correlation between all metrics was calculated, while controlling for the topology, \bar{I}_B and B_{\max} . These correlations are presented in table 6.61. For each correlation the corresponding p -value was calculated, and these p -values are presented in table 6.62.

6 Evaluation

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.5551	1.0000									
$Cons$	-0.5350	-0.5303	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.5410	-0.4286	0.9356	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.0583	0.3160	0.4289	0.3867	1.0000						
$Gini$	-0.0913	0.0864	-0.5310	-0.4262	0.7324	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	-0.2464	-0.0115	0.5343	0.4293	0.6560	0.9449	1.0000				
R	0.8721	0.6718	0.5340	-0.4289	0.0721	0.0335	-0.0781	1.0000			
H	0.8203	0.2722	-0.5129	0.6184	-0.1510	-0.0273	-0.2367	0.7176	1.0000		
SBR	-0.2082	-0.0356	0.3260	0.3034	0.5914	0.9427	0.9900	-0.0314	-0.1422	1.0000	
TPS	-0.9999	0.5551	0.3306	0.5410	0.0584	-0.0912	-0.2463	0.8721	0.8203	-0.2081	1.0000

Table 6.61: Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiments $\{ex_{P,t,1000} | P \in \{\overline{I}_B, B_{max}\}, t \in \{NET, RING\}\}$ while controlling for \overline{I}_B , \overline{I}_B and the topology.

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.0136	1.0000									
$Cons$	0.0182	0.0195	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.0168	0.0671	4.1886	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.8125	0.1875	0.0669	0.1020	1.0000						
$Gini$	0.7102	0.7249	0.0193	0.0688	0.0004	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.3092	0.9628	0.0184	0.0666	0.0023	1.1354	1.0000				
R	1.1408	0.0016	0.0185	0.0669	0.7693	0.8916	0.7508	1.0000			
H	1.6975	0.2596	0.0247	0.0048	0.5371	0.9116	0.3292	0.0005	1.0000		
SBR	0.3925	0.8851	0.1732	0.2066	0.0077	1.5919	6.8454	0.8983	0.5614	1.0000	
TPS	9.0485	0.0136	0.1668	0.0168	0.8123	0.7104	0.3093	1.1399	1.7027	0.3927	1.0000

Table 6.62: Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table 6.61.

Table 6.61 shows a positive correlation between A_{Sec} and A_{Sca} , with the corresponding p -value (table 6.62) below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows a negative correlation between $Cons$ and A_{Sca} and between $Cons$ and A_{Sec} , with the corresponding p -values (table 6.62) below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows a positive correlation between $FT_{\Delta CL}$ and A_{Sca} , with the corresponding p -value (table 6.62) below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant. Table 6.61 shows a negative correlation between $FT_{\Delta CL}$ and A_{Sec} , but the corresponding $p \approx 0.0671$ suggests that the correlation is only borderline significant. Table 6.61 shows a strong positive correlation between $FT_{\Delta CL}$ and $Cons$, but the corresponding p -value (table 6.62) is extremely high, suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows that there does not exist a correlation between $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ and A_{Sca} , but the corresponding p -value is above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant. Furthermore, table 6.61 shows weak positive correlations between $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ and A_{Sec} , between $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ and $Cons$, and between $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ and $FT_{\Delta CL}$, but all

corresponding p -values are above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows that there does not exist a correlation between $Gini$ and A_{Sca} , and between $Gini$ and A_{Sec} , but the corresponding p -values are above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows a negative correlation between $Gini$ and $Cons$ and between $Gini$ and $FT_{\Delta CL}$, whereas the correlation between $Gini$ and $Cons$ has a corresponding p -value below the threshold, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant, and the correlation between $Gini$ and $FT_{\Delta CL}$ is borderline significant with $p = 0.0688$.

Table 6.61 shows a positive correlation between $Gini$ and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, with the corresponding p -value (table 6.62) below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows a weak negative correlation between HHI_{norm} and A_{Sca} , and no correlation between HHI_{norm} and A_{Sec} , with the corresponding p -values being above the threshold of 0.05 suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant. Table 6.61 shows a positive correlation between HHI_{norm} and $Cons$, between HHI_{norm} and $FT_{\Delta CL}$, and between HHI_{norm} and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$. Table 6.62 shows that the corresponding p -values for the correlations between HHI_{norm} and $Cons$ and between HHI_{norm} and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$ are below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are statistically significant, whereas for the correlation between HHI_{norm} and $FT_{\Delta CL}$ the $p = 0.0666$ suggests that the correlation is borderline significant. Table 6.61 shows a strong positive correlation between HHI_{norm} and $Gini$, which is expected, because HHI_{norm} and $Gini$ are both measures of the distribution of tokens among validating nodes.

Table 6.61 shows positive correlations between R and A_{Sca} , R and A_{Sec} , and R and $Cons$. Table 6.62 shows that the corresponding p -values for the correlations between R and A_{Sec} , and R and $Cons$ are below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are statistically significant, while the p -value for the correlation between R and A_{Sca} is > 1 , suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant. Table 6.61 shows a negative correlation between R and $FT_{\Delta CL}$, with the corresponding $p = 0.0669$ (table 6.62), suggesting that the correlation is borderline significant. Table 6.61 shows that there does not exist a correlation between R and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, between R and $Gini$, and between R and HHI_{norm} .

Table 6.61 shows positive correlations between H and A_{Sca} , between H and $FT_{\Delta CL}$, and between H and R . Table 6.62 shows that the p -value for the correlation between H and $FT_{\Delta CL}$ and the p -value for the correlation between H and R are below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are statistically significant, while the p -value for the correlation between H and A_{Sca} is very high, suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant. Table 6.61 shows a weak correlation between H and A_{Sec} , with a p -value (table 6.62) above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that it is not statistically significant. Table 6.61 shows a negative correlation between H and $Cons$, with the corresponding p -value (table 6.62) below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant. Furthermore, table 6.61 shows that there does not exist a correlation between H and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, between H and $Gini$, and between H and HHI_{norm} , however the corresponding

p -values (table 6.62) are above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows strong positive correlations between SBR and $Gini$ and between SBR and HHI_{norm} , but both with very high corresponding p -values suggesting that the correlations are not statistically significant. Table 6.61 shows weak correlations between SBR and A_{Sca} (negative), between SBR and $Cons$ (positive), and between SBR and $FT_{\Delta CL}$ (positive), but the corresponding p -values (table 6.62) are above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant. Table 6.61 also shows a correlation between SBR and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, and the corresponding p -value (table 6.62) is below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant. Finally, table 6.61 shows that there does not exist a correlation between SBR and A_{Sec} , between SBR and R , and between SBR and H , but the corresponding p -values are above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant.

Table 6.61 shows a strong negative correlation between TPS and A_{Sca} , but the corresponding $pval \approx 9.0485$ is highly above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is not statistically significant. Table 6.61 show positive correlations between TPS and A_{Sec} , between TPS and $Cons$, and between TPS and $FT_{\Delta CL}$. The p -values for the correlations between TPS and A_{Sec} and between TPS and $FT_{\Delta CL}$ are below the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are statistically significant, while the p -value for the correlation between TPS and $Cons$ is above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant. Furthermore, table 6.61 shows that there does not exist a correlation between TPS and $FT_{\Delta TPS}$, and between TPS and $Gini$, but the corresponding p -values (table 6.62) are above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant. Table 6.61 also shows weak negative correlations between TPS and HHI_{norm} and between TPS and SBR , with the corresponding p -values being above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant. Finally, table 6.61 shows strong positive correlations between TPS and R , and between TPS and H , but the corresponding p -values are very high above the threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these correlations are not statistically significant.

7 Discussion

7.1 Principal Findings

This thesis presents 3SIM, a flexible, software-architecture-focused blockchain simulator, that helps software architects to understand how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. 3SIM, with its metamodel, simulation model and implementation, answers rQ 1.

The experiments conducted in this thesis show that the results produced by 3SIM are plausible and consistent with existing research on the blockchain trilemma.

In the conducted experiments, the scalability of a simulated blockchain system increased with an increasing *maximum block size* (B_{\max}) and with less required security confirmations. A faster P2P network, with a higher throughput and lower latency, lead to a better scalability. Scalability of the simulated blockchain system was negatively impacted by very short and very large *mean block creation interval* (\bar{I}_B), because for very short \bar{I}_B there is not enough time to propagate transactions, and for very large \bar{I}_B less transactions can be confirmed per second.

In the conducted experiments, a longer \bar{I}_B improved the security of the simulated blockchain system in terms of availability and stale block rate, however at the expense of consistency and reliability. There is an inherent trade-off between availability and consistency [5]. The security of the simulated blockchain system decreased with an increasing B_{\max} . A faster P2P network, with a higher throughput and lower latency, lead to better security of the simulated blockchain system.

In the conducted experiments, the *degree of decentralization* (DoD) of the simulated blockchain system increased with an increasingly equal distribution of hashing power among validating nodes. The experiments also show, that DoD improves if validating nodes are equally distributed across geographical regions.

Pairwise partial pearson correlations between all output metrics were calculated based on the results of the experiments where \bar{I}_B and B_{\max} was varied, controlling for \bar{I}_B and B_{\max} . In the following consider only the correlations that are statistically significant, i.e. have a corresponding *pval* below the threshold of 0.05. Negative correlations between *Cons* and A_{Sca} and *Cons* and A_{Sec} , show that there is a trade-off between consistency and availability, which is consistent with research [5]. A strong correlation between H and R , shows that a better DoD can improve the reliability of a blockchain system. However,

negative correlations between *Gini* and *Cons*, and between *H* and *Cons*, show that a better DoD can negatively impact the consistency of the blockchain system.

The results of the conducted experiments and the calculated correlations, help to better understand how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma (2).

7.2 Contributions to Practice

This thesis presents 3SIM, a flexible simulation tool that helps software architects to better understand how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma.

The metamodel of SM-SIM enables software-architecture-focused modelling of blockchain systems. The metamodel of 3SIM extends the metamodel of SM-SIM, enabling modelling of transactions instead of only blocks, enabling modelling of different inbound and outbound traffic characteristics for links between validating nodes, and enabling modelling geographical regions of validating nodes.

3SIM helps software architects to quickly and iteratively model blockchain systems, and assess how the blockchain trilemma manifests in the modelled blockchain system, without the need to deploy a real-world blockchain system for each iteration. This saves practitioners costs and time, because they do not need to refactor as often, and because setting up real-world blockchain systems is costly and tedious [8].

7.3 Contributions to Research

3SIM is a blockchain simulator, that computes several *output metrics* suitable to operationalize the subconcepts of the *blockchain trilemma* [5]. 3SIM allows researchers to quickly investigate the blockchain trilemma based on models of blockchain system configurations.

Several experiments were conducted, that give researchers a better understanding of how the output metrics produced by 3SIM are correlated, and how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. Hereby, researchers can gain a better understanding of the blockchain trilemma.

7.4 Limitations

3SIM only supports simulating blockchain systems that use PoW-based consensus protocols with the longest chain rule for fork resolution. 3SIM only allows simulating blockchain systems, and does not allow simulating alternative *distributed ledger technologies (DLTs)*, such as *blockDAG*.

The simulation results of 3SIM were not quantitatively verified in terms of accuracy. Existing research was used to demonstrate the plausibility of the results produced by 3SIM. However, the accuracy of the results produced by 3SIM was not evaluated.

7.5 Future Research

More relevant metrics to operationalize the *blockchain trilemma* could be identified and added to 3SIM, in future research.

3SIM does not simulate *mining pools*, which influence the DoD of a blockchain system [2]. 3SIM does also not simulate *smart contracts*, that influence various subconcepts of the blockchain trilemma [9]. In future research, 3SIM could be extended to enable simulating mining pools and smart contracts.

Future research could extend 3SIM to enable simulating blockchain systems with alternative consensus protocols, e.g. *Proof-of-Stake (PoS)*, or extend 3SIM to enable simulating alternative DLTs, e.g. *blockDAG*.

3SIM extended the metamodel and simulation model of SM-SIM. The improvements made to the metamodel and simulation model in this thesis, could be ported back into SM-SIM in future research. For example, 3SIM allows simulating individual transactions, while SM-SIM only simulates blocks.

Furthermore, future research could assess the accuracy of results produced by 3SIM, by comparing them to real-world blockchain systems, or by using a machine-learning-based approach to validate simulation results, like Gouda et al. used to evaluate their blockchain simulator [25].

8 Conclusion

This thesis presents 3SIM, a flexible, software-architecture-focused blockchain simulator, that helps software architects to understand how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. 3SIM comprises a metamodel, that extends the metamodel of SM-SIM [8], and a simulation model. 3SIM is a discrete-event simulator that uses a stochastic simulation model. 3SIM is based on *Palladio* [48] and can be run as an Eclipse plugin.

Experiments are conducted to demonstrate the plausibility and utility of results produced by 3SIM. In each experiment, an input parameter was varied while the other input parameters remained as in a common base configuration, in order to assess the influence of the varied parameter on the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma. The varied parameters are *mean block creation interval* (\bar{I}_B), *maximum block size* (B_{\max}), *throughput and latency* of links between validating nodes, *number of required security confirmations* ($n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$), and *hashing power distribution* among validating nodes. The results of these experiments are also used to investigate how several metrics suitable to operationalize blockchain trilemma subconcepts, are correlated.

The conducted experiments show, that scalability of a blockchain system improves with longer \bar{I}_B and less $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$. Very short and very large \bar{I}_B negatively impact scalability. A longer \bar{I}_B improves the security of a blockchain system in terms of availability, but at the cost of consistency, which is an inherent trade-off [5]. A faster P2P network facilitates better scalability and security. *degree of decentralization* (DoD) improves if validating nodes have an equal distribution of hashing power and are equally distributed across geographical regions.

The goals of this thesis are to design a flexible simulation tool that helps software architects better understand how blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma, and to use that tool to investigate how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma.

3SIM currently only supports simulating blockchain systems that use PoW-based consensus protocols with the longest chain rule for fork resolution. Future work could extend 3SIM to enable simulating blockchain systems with alternative consensus protocols. Furthermore, the improvements introduced by 3SIM could be ported back to SM-SIM.

The simulation results of 3SIM were not quantitatively verified in terms of accuracy. Existing research was used to demonstrate the plausibility of the results produced by 3SIM. Future research could assess the accuracy of results produced by 3SIM, by comparing them to

real-world blockchain systems, or by using a machine-learning-based approach to validate simulation results, like Gouda et al. used to evaluate their blockchain simulator [25].

In conclusion, 3SIM is a valuable tool for practitioners and researchers, to better understand how different blockchain system configurations influence the manifestation of the blockchain trilemma.

Acronyms

B_{\max} *maximum block size*

\overline{I}_B *mean block creation interval*

$\overline{I}_{\text{trx}}$ *mean transaction creation interval*

$n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ *number of required security confirmations*

DoD *degree of decentralization*

Bibliography

- [1] Niclas Kannengießer et al. *What Does Not Fit Can Be Made to Fit! Trade-Offs in Distributed Ledger Technology Designs*. SSRN Scholarly Paper 3270859. Rochester, NY, Jan. 10, 2019. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.3270859. URL: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3270859> (visited on 12/22/2023).
- [2] Niclas Kannengießer et al. “Trade-Offs between Distributed Ledger Technology Characteristics”. EN. In: *ACM Computing Surveys* 53.2 (Apr. 2020). DOI: 10.1145/3379463.
- [3] Sergey Smetanin et al. “Modeling of Distributed Ledgers: Challenges and Future Perspectives”. In: *2020 IEEE 22nd Conference on Business Informatics (CBI)*. 2020 IEEE 22nd Conference on Business Informatics (CBI). Vol. 1. ISSN: 2378-1971. June 2020, pp. 162–171. DOI: 10.1109/CBI49978.2020.00025. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9140280> (visited on 12/23/2023).
- [4] Bela Shrimali and Hiren B. Patel. “Blockchain state-of-the-art: architecture, use cases, consensus, challenges and opportunities”. In: *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences* 34.9 (Oct. 1, 2022). ZSCC: 0000184, pp. 6793–6807. ISSN: 1319-1578. DOI: 10.1016/j.jksuci.2021.08.005. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S131915782100207X> (visited on 02/22/2025).
- [5] Mansur Aliyu, Niclas Kannengießer, and Ali Sunyaev. *From Concept to Measurement: A Survey of How the Blockchain Trilemma Can Be Analyzed*. 2025. DOI: 10.48550/arxiv.2505.03768. arXiv: 2505.03768.
- [6] Gianmaria Del Monte, Diego Pennino, and Maurizio Pizzonia. “Scaling blockchains without giving up decentralization and security: a solution to the blockchain scalability trilemma”. In: *Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Cryptocurrencies and Blockchains for Distributed Systems*. CryBlock '20. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Sept. 21, 2020, pp. 71–76. ISBN: 9781450380799. DOI: 10.1145/3410699.3413800. (Visited on 06/29/2024).
- [7] Taishi Nakai et al. “The Blockchain Trilemma Described by a Formula”. In: *2023 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain (Blockchain)*. 2023, pp. 41–46. DOI: 10.1109/Blockchain60715.2023.00016.
- [8] Yannik Sproll et al. *SM-SIM: A Simulator for Selfish-Mining Attacks in Blockchain Systems*. 2025.
- [9] Niclas Kannengießer et al. “Challenges and Common Solutions in Smart Contract Development”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* (2021), pp. 4291–4318. ISSN: 0098-5589, 1939-3520, 2326-3881. DOI: 10.1109/TSE.2021.3116808. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9555611/>.

- [10] Satoshi Nakamoto. *Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System*. 2008. URL: <https://bitcoin.org/en/bitcoin-paper> (visited on 01/17/2024).
- [11] Ali Sunyaev. “Distributed Ledger Technology”. In: ed. by Ali Sunyaev. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 265–299. ISBN: 9783030349578. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-34957-8_9. (Visited on 12/25/2023).
- [12] Yang Xiao et al. “A Survey of Distributed Consensus Protocols for Blockchain Networks”. In: *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials* 22.2 (2020), pp. 1432–1465. ISSN: 1553-877X, 2373-745X. DOI: 10.1109/COMST.2020.2969706. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8972381/>.
- [13] Sarada Prasad Gochhayat et al. “Measuring Decentrality in Blockchain Based Systems”. In: *IEEE Access* 8 (2020), pp. 178372–178390. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3026577.
- [14] Arthur Gervais et al. “On the Security and Performance of Proof of Work Blockchains”. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*. CCS ’16. New York, NY, USA, 2016, pp. 3–16. ISBN: 978-1-4503-4139-4. DOI: 10.1145/2976749.2978341.
- [15] Esra Bas. “A Brief Introduction to Point Process, Counting Process, Renewal Process, Regenerative Process, Poisson Process”. In: *Basics of Probability and Stochastic Processes*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 131–147. ISBN: 978-3-030-32323-3. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-32323-3_9.
- [16] Hervé Abdi. “Coefficient of variation”. In: *Encyclopedia of research design* 1.5 (2010), pp. 169–171.
- [17] *Covariance – from Wolfram MathWorld – mathworld.wolfram.com*. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/Covariance.html>. [Accessed 10-09-2025].
- [18] *Statistical Correlation – from Wolfram MathWorld – mathworld.wolfram.com*. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/StatisticalCorrelation.html>. [Accessed 10-09-2025].
- [19] Ruud Wetzels and Eric-Jan Wagenmakers. “A default Bayesian hypothesis test for correlations and partial correlations”. In: *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review* 19.6 (July 2012), pp. 1057–1064. ISSN: 1531-5320. DOI: 10.3758/s13423-012-0295-x.
- [20] Nikolaos Pandis. “Calculating the P value and carrying out a statistical test”. In: *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics* 148.1 (2015), pp. 187–188.
- [21] Remigijus Paulavičius, Saulius Grigaitis, and Ernestas Filatovas. “A Systematic Review and Empirical Analysis of Blockchain Simulators”. In: *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), pp. 38010–38028. ISSN: 2169-3536. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3063324. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9366733> (visited on 01/19/2024).
- [22] Adel Albshri et al. “Blockchain Simulators: A Systematic Mapping Study”. In: *2022 IEEE International Conference on Services Computing (SCC)*. 2022, pp. 284–294. DOI: 10.1109/SCC55611.2022.00049.

- [23] Bozhi Wang et al. “A Simulation Approach for Studying Behavior and Quality of Blockchain Networks”. In: *Blockchain – ICBC 2018*. Ed. by Shiping Chen, Harry Wang, and Liang-Jie Zhang. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 18–31. ISBN: 9783319944784. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-94478-4_2.
- [24] Ittay Eyal and Emin Gün Sirer. “Majority is not enough: bitcoin mining is vulnerable”. In: *Commun. ACM* 61.7 (June 2018), pp. 95–102. ISSN: 0001-0782. DOI: 10.1145/3212998.
- [25] Deepak Kumar Gouda, Shashwat Jolly, and Kalpesh Kapoor. “Design and Validation of BlockEval, A Blockchain Simulator”. In: *2021 International Conference on Communication Systems & NETWORKS (COMSNETS)*. 2021 International Conference on Communication Systems & NETWORKS (COMSNETS). ISSN: 2155-2509. Jan. 2021, pp. 281–289. DOI: 10.1109/COMSNETS51098.2021.9352838. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9352838> (visited on 06/29/2024).
- [26] Julien Polge et al. “BlockPerf: A Hybrid Blockchain Emulator/Simulator Framework”. In: *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), pp. 107858–107872. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3101044.
- [27] Maher Alharby and Aad van Moorsel. “BlockSim: A Simulation Framework for Blockchain Systems”. In: *SIGMETRICS Perform. Eval. Rev.* 46.3 (Jan. 2019), pp. 135–138. ISSN: 0163-5999. DOI: 10.1145/3308897.3308956.
- [28] Carlos Faria and Miguel Correia. “BlockSim: Blockchain Simulator”. In: *2019 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain (Blockchain)*. 2019, pp. 439–446. DOI: 10.1109/Blockchain.2019.00067.
- [29] Santosh Pandey et al. “BlockSIM: A practical simulation tool for optimal network design, stability and planning”. In: *2019 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain and Cryptocurrency (ICBC)*. 2019, pp. 133–137. DOI: 10.1109/BL0C.2019.8751320.
- [30] Nandini Agrawal et al. *BlockSim-Net: A Network Based Blockchain Simulator*. 2020. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.2011.03241.
- [31] Bo Cui and Yun Hu. “BSELA: A Blockchain Simulator with Event-Layered Architecture”. In: *Future Generation Computer Systems* 151 (Feb. 2024), pp. 182–195. ISSN: 0167-739X. DOI: 10.1016/j.future.2023.09.034.
- [32] Xuyang Ma et al. “CBlockSim: A Modular High-Performance Blockchain Simulator”. In: *2022 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain and Cryptocurrency (ICBC)*. 2022 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain and Cryptocurrency (ICBC). May 2022, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/ICBC54727.2022.9805504. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9805504> (visited on 06/29/2024).
- [33] Bozhi Wang et al. “ChainSim: A P2P Blockchain Simulation Framework”. In: *Blockchain Technology and Application*. Springer Singapore, 2021, pp. 1–16. ISBN: 9789813364783. DOI: 10.1007/978-981-33-6478-3_1.
- [34] Maher Alharby et al. “Data-Driven Model-Based Analysis of the Ethereum Verifier’s Dilemma”. In: *2020 50th Annual IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks (DSN)*. 2020, pp. 209–220. DOI: 10.1109/DSN48063.2020.00038.

- [35] Zi Hau Chin, Timothy Tzen Vun Yap, and Ian K. T. Tan. “Simulating Difficulty Adjustment in Blockchain with SimBlock”. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM International Symposium on Blockchain and Secure Critical Infrastructure*. BSCI ’20. Taipei, Taiwan: Association for Computing Machinery, 2020, pp. 192–197. ISBN: 9781450376105. DOI: 10.1145/3384943.3409437.
- [36] Aditya Deshpande, Pezhman Nasirifard, and Hans-Arno Jacobsen. “eVIBES: Configurable and Interactive Ethereum Blockchain Simulation Framework”. In: *Proceedings of the 19th International Middleware Conference (Posters)*. Middleware ’18. Rennes, France: Association for Computing Machinery, 2018, pp. 11–12. ISBN: 9781450361095. DOI: 10.1145/3284014.3284020.
- [37] Mariano Basile et al. “On Improving SimBlock Blockchain Simulator”. In: *2021 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*. 2021 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC). ISSN: 2642-7389. Sept. 2021, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/ISCC53001.2021.9631470. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9631470> (visited on 06/29/2024).
- [38] Ryohei Banno and Kazuyuki Shudo. “Simulating a Blockchain Network with SimBlock”. In: *2019 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain and Cryptocurrency (ICBC)*. 2019, pp. 3–4. DOI: 10.1109/BLOC.2019.8751431.
- [39] Lina Alsahan, Nouredine Lasla, and Mohamed Abdallah. “Local Bitcoin Network Simulator for Performance Evaluation using Lightweight Virtualization”. In: *2020 IEEE International Conference on Informatics, IoT, and Enabling Technologies (ICIOT)*. 2020, pp. 355–360. DOI: 10.1109/ICIOT48696.2020.9089630.
- [40] Edoardo Rosa, Gabriele D’Angelo, and Stefano Ferretti. “Agent-Based Simulation of Blockchains”. In: *Methods and Applications for Modeling and Simulation of Complex Systems*. Ed. by Gary Tan et al. Communications in Computer and Information Science. Singapore: Springer, 2019, pp. 115–126. ISBN: 9789811510786. DOI: 10.1007/978-981-15-1078-6_10.
- [41] Raheel Ahmed Memon et al. “Modeling of Blockchain Based Systems Using Queuing Theory Simulation”. In: *2018 15th International Computer Conference on Wavelet Active Media Technology and Information Processing (ICCWAMTIP)*. 2018, pp. 107–111. DOI: 10.1109/ICCWAMTIP.2018.8632560.
- [42] Andrew Miller and Rob Jansen. “Shadow-Bitcoin: Scalable Simulation via Direct Execution of Multi-Threaded Applications”. In: *8th Workshop on Cyber Security Experimentation and Test (CSET 15)*. Washington, D.C.: USENIX Association, Aug. 2015. URL: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/cset15/workshop-program/presentation/miller>.
- [43] Seyed Mehdi Fattahi, Adetokunbo Makanju, and Amin Milani Fard. “SIMBA: An Efficient Simulator for Blockchain Applications”. In: *2020 50th Annual IEEE-IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks-Supplemental Volume (DSN-S)*. 2020, pp. 51–52. DOI: 10.1109/DSN-S50200.2020.00028.
- [44] Yusuke Aoki et al. “SimBlock: A Blockchain Network Simulator”. In: *IEEE INFOCOM 2019 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*. 2019, pp. 325–329. DOI: 10.1109/INFCOMW.2019.8845253.

- [45] Francesco Bruschi et al. “Mine with it or sell it: the superhashing power dilemma”. In: *SIGMETRICS Perform. Eval. Rev.* 46.3 (Jan. 2019), pp. 127–130. ISSN: 0163-5999. DOI: 10.1145/3308897.3308954.
- [46] Elli Androulaki et al. “Evaluating User Privacy in Bitcoin”. In: *Financial Cryptography and Data Security*. Ed. by Ahmad-Reza Sadeghi. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 34–51. ISBN: 978-3-642-39884-1.
- [47] Lyubomir Stoykov, Kaiwen Zhang, and Hans-Arno Jacobsen. “VIBES: fast blockchain simulations for large-scale peer-to-peer networks: demo”. In: *Proceedings of the 18th ACM/IFIP/USENIX Middleware Conference: Posters and Demos*. Middleware ’17. Las Vegas, Nevada: Association for Computing Machinery, 2017, pp. 19–20. ISBN: 9781450352017. DOI: 10.1145/3155016.3155020.
- [48] Ralf Reussner et al., eds. *Modeling and simulating software architectures. The Palladio approach*. Description based on publisher supplied metadata and other sources. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2016. 1377 pp. ISBN: 9780262336789.
- [49] Thomas Goldschmidt, Steffen Becker, and Erik Burger. “Towards a tool-oriented taxonomy of view-based modelling”. In: *Modellierung 2012*. Bonn: Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V., 2012, pp. 59–74. ISBN: 978-3-88579-295-6.
- [50] Jerry Banks and John S. Carson. “Introduction to discrete-event simulation”. In: *Proceedings of the 18th Conference on Winter Simulation*. WSC ’86. Washington, D.C., USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 1986, pp. 17–23. ISBN: 0911801111. DOI: 10.1145/318242.318253.
- [51] Christian Decker and Roger Wattenhofer. “Information propagation in the Bitcoin network”. In: *IEEE P2P 2013 Proceedings*. 2013, pp. 1–10. DOI: 10.1109/P2P.2013.6688704.
- [52] Luca Ardito et al. “Effectiveness of Kotlin vs. Java in android app development tasks”. In: *Information and Software Technology* 127 (Nov. 2020), p. 106374. ISSN: 0950-5849. DOI: 10.1016/j.infsof.2020.106374.
- [53] Eclipse. *Eclipse EMF*. Mar. 2025. URL: <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/modeling.emf.emf>.
- [54] Eclipse. *Eclipse tycho*. June 2024. URL: <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.tycho>.

A Appendix

A.1 Experiment Results Charts Summary

This section provides an overview of all charts with results of all conducted experiments.

Figure A.1: Results of the experiment varying \bar{I}_B for each output metric. **Part I.**

Figure A.2: Results of the experiment varying \bar{I}_B for each output metric. *Part II.*

Figure A.3: Results of the experiment varying B_{\max} for each output metric. *Part I.*

Figure A.4: Results of the experiment varying B_{\max} for each output metric. *Part II.*

Figure A.5: Results of the experiment with different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes, for each output metric. **Part I.**

Figure A.6: Results of the experiment with different distributions of hashing power among validating nodes, for each output metric. *Part II.*

Figure A.7: Results of the experiment with different throughput and latency of links between validating nodes, for each output metric. *Part I.*

Figure A.8: Results of the experiment with different throughput and latency of links between validating nodes, for each output metric. *Part II.*

Figure A.9: Results of the experiment varying $n_{security_confirmation}$ for each output metric. **Part I.**

Figure A.10: Results of the experiment varying $n_{\text{security_confirmation}}$ for each output metric. **Part II.**

A.2 Pairwise Pearson Correlations

Based on the simulation results of the experiments $\text{ex}_{\bar{I}_B, \text{NET}, 1000}^-$, $\text{ex}_{\bar{I}_B, \text{NET}, 1000}^-$, $\text{ex}_{B_{\max}, \text{NET}, 1000}$, $\text{ex}_{B_{\max}, \text{RING}, 1000}$ the pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1 was calculated, while controlling for the parameter that was varied in the experiment (\bar{I}_B or B_{\max} respectively). For each correlation the corresponding p -value was calculated. Tables A.1, A.3, A.5 and A.7 present the pairwise partial pearson correlations, and tables A.2, A.4, A.6 and A.8 present the corresponding p -values.

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	Cons	$FT_{\Delta\text{CL}}$	$FT_{\Delta\text{TPS}}$	Gini	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.9932	1.0000									
Cons	-0.9920	-0.9920	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta\text{CL}}$	-0.9934	-0.9934	0.9979	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta\text{TPS}}$	0.9940	0.9745	0.9368	0.9123	1.0000						
Gini	-0.9032	-0.9470	0.9920	0.9934	-0.8508	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	-0.9223	-0.9611	0.9920	0.9934	-0.8745	0.9989	1.0000				
R	-0.8794	-0.8180	0.9920	0.9934	-0.9262	0.5898	0.6272	1.0000			
H	-0.9419	-0.9746	0.9920	0.9934	-0.8995	0.9949	0.9985	0.6685	1.0000		
SBR	-0.9853	-0.9985	-0.8028	-0.7629	-0.9607	0.9632	0.9748	0.7852	0.9854	1.0000	
TPS	1.0000	0.9931	0.8932	0.8625	0.9941	-0.9028	-0.9220	-0.8798	-0.9417	-0.9852	1.0000

Table A.1: Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $\text{ex}_{\bar{I}_B, \text{NET}, 1000}^-$ while controlling for \bar{I}_B .

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	Cons	$FT_{\Delta\text{CL}}$	$FT_{\Delta\text{TPS}}$	Gini	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.0743	1.0000									
Cons	0.0803	0.0803	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta\text{CL}}$	0.0733	0.0733	0.0409	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta\text{TPS}}$	0.0698	0.1441	0.2276	0.2686	1.0000						
Gini	0.2825	0.2082	0.0803	0.0733	0.3523	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.2525	0.1782	0.0803	0.0733	0.3223	0.0299	1.0000				
R	0.3159	0.3902	0.0803	0.0733	0.2461	0.5984	0.5684	1.0000			
H	0.2180	0.1437	0.0803	0.0733	0.2878	0.0645	0.0345	0.5339	1.0000		
SBR	0.1092	0.0349	0.4067	0.4476	0.1790	0.1733	0.1433	0.4251	0.1088	1.0000	
TPS	0.0005	0.0748	0.2969	0.3378	0.0693	0.2830	0.2531	0.3154	0.2185	0.1098	1.0000

Table A.2: Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.1.

A Appendix

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.5962	1.0000									
$Cons$	-0.8464	-0.8464	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	-0.7255	-0.7255	0.8748	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	-0.5313	-0.8875	-0.0859	-0.5089	1.0000						
$Gini$	0.6505	0.1613	0.8464	0.7255	0.0737	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.6615	0.1651	0.8464	0.7255	0.0679	-1.0000	1.0000				
R	0.9135	0.8001	-0.8464	-0.7255	-0.6754	0.4628	0.4700	1.0000			
H	0.9079	0.4631	-0.8465	0.9435	-0.2739	0.9036	0.9097	0.7762	1.0000		
SBR	0.7484	0.2492	0.8464	0.8518	-0.0345	0.9903	0.9923	0.5641	0.9530	1.0000	
TPS	-1.0000	0.5962	0.7806	0.8840	-0.5313	0.6504	0.6614	0.9136	0.9079	0.7483	1.0000

Table A.3: Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{B_{max},NET,1000}$ while controlling for B_{max} .

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.2117	1.0000									
$Cons$	0.0336	0.0336	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.1026	0.1027	0.0225	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.2781	0.0183	0.8715	0.3026	1.0000						
$Gini$	0.1619	0.7602	0.0336	0.1027	0.8896	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.1525	0.7546	0.0336	0.1027	0.8983	0.0000	1.0000				
R	0.0109	0.0560	0.0336	0.1027	0.1410	0.3554	0.3469	1.0000			
H	0.0123	0.3550	0.0336	0.0047	0.5995	0.0135	0.0119	0.0695	1.0000		
SBR	0.0870	0.6340	0.0336	0.0313	0.9482	0.0001	8.7793	0.2436	0.0033	1.0000	
TPS	1.8489	0.2116	0.0669	0.0194	0.2780	0.1620	0.1526	0.0109	0.0123	0.0871	1.0000

Table A.4: Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.3.

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.9199	1.0000									
$Cons$	0.9615	-0.9615	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.9625	-0.9625	0.9986	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.9820	0.9775	0.9739	0.9604	1.0000						
$Gini$	-0.8139	-0.9765	-0.9615	-0.9625	-0.9091	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	-0.8117	-0.9757	0.9615	0.9625	-0.9075	1.0000	1.0000				
R	-0.9984	-0.8963	0.9615	0.9625	-0.9697	0.7798	0.7774	1.0000			
H	0.7139	0.3823	-0.9615	-0.9625	0.5687	-0.1742	-0.1705	-0.7524	1.0000		
SBR	-0.7704	-0.9587	-0.7451	-0.7085	-0.8771	0.9975	0.9977	0.7332	-0.1036	1.0000	
TPS	-1.0000	0.9199	0.9992	0.9958	0.9820	-0.8139	-0.8117	-0.9984	0.7140	-0.7704	1.0000

Table A.5: Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{\bar{I}_B,RING,1000}$ while controlling for \bar{I}_B .

A Appendix

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.2565	1.0000									
$Cons$	0.1772	0.1772	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.1748	0.1748	0.0340	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.1211	0.1354	0.1458	0.1798	1.0000						
$Gini$	0.3947	0.1382	0.1772	0.1748	0.2736	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.3971	0.1406	0.1772	0.1748	0.2760	0.0024	1.0000				
R	0.0360	0.2925	0.1772	0.1748	0.1571	0.4307	0.4331	1.0000			
H	0.4938	0.7503	0.1772	0.1748	0.6149	0.8885	0.8909	0.4578	1.0000		
SBR	0.4401	0.1836	0.4648	0.4988	0.3190	0.0454	0.0430	0.4761	0.9339	1.0000	
TPS	1.2872	0.2565	0.0247	0.0587	0.1211	0.3947	0.3971	0.0360	0.4938	0.4401	1.0000

Table A.6: Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.5.

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.6400	1.0000									
$Cons$	-0.9063	-0.9063	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	-0.8184	-0.8184	0.9659	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.9310	0.4819	0.8542	0.8891	1.0000						
$Gini$	0.5759	0.2651	0.9063	0.8184	0.8164	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.4500	0.1845	0.9063	0.8184	0.7266	0.9878	1.0000				
R	0.9402	0.8500	-0.9063	-0.8184	0.8284	0.4981	0.3759	1.0000			
H	0.8814	0.5122	-0.9063	0.8183	0.9856	0.8832	0.8081	0.8132	1.0000		
SBR	0.4245	0.1935	0.9653	0.8961	0.7070	0.9788	0.9973	0.3637	0.7952	1.0000	
TPS	-1.0000	0.6400	0.6289	0.7385	0.9310	0.5759	0.4500	0.9403	0.8814	0.4246	1.0000

Table A.7: Pairwise partial pearson correlation between all output metrics listed in table 2.1, based on results of experiment $ex_{B_{max}, RING, 1000}$ while controlling for B_{max} .

Metric	A_{Sca}	A_{Sec}	$Cons$	$FT_{\Delta CL}$	$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	$Gini$	HHI_{norm}	R	H	SBR	TPS
A_{Sca}	1.0000										
A_{Sec}	0.1711	1.0000									
$Cons$	0.0128	0.0128	1.0000								
$FT_{\Delta CL}$	0.0465	0.0465	0.0017	1.0000							
$FT_{\Delta TPS}$	0.0070	0.3331	0.0303	0.0178	1.0000						
$Gini$	0.2317	0.6117	0.0128	0.0465	0.0475	1.0000					
HHI_{norm}	0.3706	0.7263	0.0128	0.0465	0.1019	0.0002	1.0000				
R	0.0053	0.0320	0.0128	0.0465	0.0416	0.3146	0.4626	1.0000			
H	0.0203	0.2989	0.0128	0.0465	0.0003	0.0197	0.0517	0.0491	1.0000		
SBR	0.4014	0.7134	0.0018	0.0156	0.1162	0.0007	1.0976	0.4785	0.0586	1.0000	
TPS	0.0000	0.1710	0.1810	0.0936	0.0070	0.2316	0.3705	0.0052	0.0203	0.4014	1.0000

Table A.8: Corresponding p -values for the correlations presented in table A.7.